

E5.3 Final Prototype of Operational Components and Toolkit for Automated Discovery and SLA Assurance v1.0

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**6G Networks Enabled through
Technology Driven Solutions
[6GENABLERS]**

**Programa de Universalización de
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List of Acronyms

6G	Sixth Generation
API	Application Programming Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DID	Distributed Identifier
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
FAMD	Factorial Analysis of Mixed Data
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
ID	Identifier
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LLM	Large Language Model
ML	Machine Learning
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OAS	OpenAPI Specification
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAM	Random Access Memory
REST	Representational State Transfer
RF	Random Forest
SCSC	Smart Contract State Composer
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SSE	Sum of Squared Errors
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VNF	Virtual Network Function

Executive Summary

This document corresponds to deliverable *E5.3 Final Prototype of Operational Components and Toolkit for Automated Discovery and SLA Assurance*, as part of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project (TSI-063000-2021-12). Building on the pioneering work of E5.2, this deliverable marks a significant milestone in advancing Telecom Marketplaces. It centers on the final development and implementation of two critical modules within the Smart Discovery system: the Clustering and Classification module and the Intent-based Discovery module. The primary objective of E5.3 is to present the final prototype of operational components that automate the discovery process within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. The document provides a detailed examination of the enhanced design specifications, extended functionalities, refined architecture, and updated deployment strategies for both modules. It offers a comprehensive narrative that delves into the intricacies of the prototype's development and highlights the improvements made since the initial version presented in E5.2. The contributions of E5.3 extend beyond individual modules, envisioning a Telecom Marketplace where stakeholders can engage seamlessly with automated, user-friendly, and robust systems. This deliverable sets the stage for future advancements, reinforcing the 6GENABLERS-DLT project's commitment to innovation and excellence in the dynamic field of telecommunications.

1 Introduction

To cater to the varied requirements of applications and users, the shift towards Telecom Marketplaces demands active participation from a broad spectrum of stakeholders, including equipment manufacturers, network operators, cloud service providers, and application developers. Integrating these diverse entities and facilitating multi-functional services within a single environment introduces significant challenges, such as increased operational complexity and issues related to privacy and trust in the evolving telecom landscape.

To address these challenges, establishing resilient and distributed Marketplaces is essential for enabling effective sharing of network resources and services among stakeholders. Developing automated discovery methods that can efficiently and accurately classify and identify available offers, based on user intents, is central to this effort.

In response to the need for efficient and user-oriented Telecom Marketplaces, this deliverable E5.3 - "Final Prototype of Operational Components and Toolkit for Automated Discovery and SLA Assurance," is pivotal. It underscores the 6GENABLERS-DLT project's commitment to building a sophisticated and responsive ecosystem, where offers relevant to the consumer expectations can be quickly discerned from the large pool of exposed resources and services.

This deliverable marks the final stage in the development of a Smart Discovery system within the broader 6GENABLERS Marketplace, a key outcome of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project. As depicted in Figure 1-1, the Smart Discovery system includes two main modules: Clustering and Classification, and Intent-based Discovery. Together, these modules provide a comprehensive toolkit for automated discovery, addressing the complex challenges posed by diverse network offerings. In short, this toolkit participates in the offer creation process, for the smart classification of incoming offers, and during the offers' retrieval, by allowing the interaction with the platform via intents.

Figure 1-1. Overview of the Smart Discovery system

This document details the enhancements and improvements made to the prototype, providing insights into the final design specifications (including targeted scope, covered functionalities and refined architecture), as well as the final implementation aspects and deployment strategies of the Clustering and Classification, and Intent-based Discovery modules. E5.3 aims to significantly advance the development of Telecom Marketplaces, enabling stakeholders to seamlessly engage and leverage the trading of network resources while managing the inherent complexities of the telecom landscape.

In summary, E5.3 represents the culmination of design and implementation efforts related to the automated discovery feature of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace developed within the 6GENABLERS-DLT project. This document exemplifies our dedication to innovation and progress in the dynamic areas of distributed ledger technology and telecommunications, envisioning a future where stakeholder collaboration is facilitated through automated and user-centric Telecom Marketplaces.

1.1 Document Scope and Objectives

The purpose of this document is to provide comprehensive guidelines for the installation, operation, and integration of the final prototype components and toolkit for automated discovery within the 6GENABLERS-DLT project. This deliverable, E5.3, updates the previous deliverable E5.2 by incorporating operational extensions, improvements, and modifications based on the feedback and experiences from the initial validation phase.

This document covers the following key areas:

1. Final Prototype Implementation: Detailed description of the final version of the platform components related to the Smart Discovery system. This includes the functionalities, architecture, and interfaces of each component.
2. Operational Updates: Explanation of the updates performed to the modules since the initial prototype.
3. Installation Guidelines: Step-by-step instructions for installing the software modules, ensuring that they compile correctly and are free of errors.
4. Operation Guidelines: Detailed operational procedures for using the software modules, including troubleshooting tips and best practices.
5. Integration Instructions: Guidelines for integrating the automated discovery components with other systems within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

The primary objectives of this document are:

1. Provide Clear and Detailed Instructions: Ensure that all users, including developers, operators, and system integrators, have access to clear, detailed, and easy-to-follow instructions for the installation and operation of the final prototype of the Smart Discovery system.
2. Facilitate Smooth Integration: Support the seamless integration of the automated discovery components into the existing infrastructure, minimizing potential disruptions and maximizing efficiency.
3. Incorporate Feedback and Improvements: Reflect the enhancements made based on the feedback from the initial prototype operation, ensuring that the final prototype meets the project's requirements and stakeholders' expectations.

4. Ensure Robustness and Reliability: Present the final prototype as a reliable and robust solution, with all components thoroughly tested to be error-free and compliant with the described functionalities.
5. Enhance User Experience: Provide a well-structured document that enhances the user experience by offering comprehensive support, troubleshooting advice, and operational best practices.

By achieving these objectives, this document aims to serve as a definitive guide for the successful deployment and operation of the automated discovery toolkit, contributing to the overall success of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

1.2 Relation to the Project’s Activities

This deliverable closes the report of outcomes from Work Package 5 (P5), which focuses on the pillars related to Smart Discovery and Service Level Agreement (SLA) Assurance. Work Package 5 investigates and develops novel approaches to assist in the discovery and selection of Marketplace offers, accompanied by the monitoring and tracking of SLA terms fulfilment. The core areas of this work package include:

- **Smart Discovery:** Developing innovative techniques and tools to automate and enhance the process of discovering suitable offers within a digital marketplace. This involves leveraging advanced algorithms and data analytics to identify and select the best available options that meet specific user requirements.
- **SLA Assurance:** Establishing mechanisms to ensure that the terms of service level agreements are met. This includes real-time monitoring, tracking, and validation of SLA terms to provide transparency and accountability, ensuring that both service providers and consumers adhere to the agreed standards.

By addressing these pillars, Work Package 5 aims to create a robust framework that enhances the efficiency and reliability of digital marketplaces, ensuring that users can discover and select offers that meet their needs while maintaining high standards of service quality through effective SLA management.

Figure 1-2. E5.3 positioning and relation to the project’s activities

As depicted in Figure 1-2, deliverable E5.3 is the joint result of the work done in the two tasks within P5, which are listed below.

- A5.1 – Dynamic Resource Discovery: This task focuses on the automated identification and selection of distributed resources from multiple administrative domains. In order to execute selection and ordering of offers for trading settlement, this task is meant to enrich the customer experience when interacting with the Marketplace via advanced and smart strategies to meet searching criteria.
- A5.2 – Proactive SLA Assurance: This task focuses on automating SLA signing underpinned by the Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) capabilities. Moreover, it is meant to keep track of contract conditions and Quality of Service (QoS) measurements, ensuring violations are recorded on the ledger, as mechanisms for SLA assurance. Finally, this task will be interlinked to A5.1 in order to trigger the smart discovery of Marketplace offers as a means to avoid potential SLA violations.

Within this context, this document is intended to fulfil the part related to task A5.1, focused on the Automated Discovery. A similar document will be also generated for the part of SLA Assurance corresponding to the work of task A5.2.

The work captured in this deliverable takes as inputs the system design and the initial prototype implementation reported in the previous deliverables of this task (E5.1 [1] and E5.2 [2]). At the same time, the implementation aspects of the different components to be developed within P5 and provided in this document will feed any required fine-tuning or refinement of the overall 6GENABLERS Marketplace architecture to be reported in the upcoming deliverable E2.3 as part of A2.6 (“DLT-anchored Smart Marketplace Architecture”).

1.3 Structure of the Document

The current document is structured in several sections to provide a comprehensive understanding of the implementation details of the final prototype for the Smart Discovery system. In particular, the document is structured as follows:

- Section 1: This section offers a holistic overview of the document, presenting its objectives, contextualizing its significance within the 6GENABLERS-DLT project, and outlining the overall structure. Moreover, it summarizes the updates performed in this deliverable with respect to its predecessor E5.2 [2].
- Section 2: This section is dedicated to one of the internal modules of the Smart Discovery system, namely the Clustering and Classification. It delves into its scope and functionalities, architecture, implementation and deployment aspects, as well as the functional tests performed to verify its correct operation.
- Section 3: Similar to Section 2, this section focuses on the Intent-based Discovery module, providing detailed information on its scope and functionalities, architecture, implementation and deployment aspects, as well as the functional and integration tests performed to verify its correct operation and interaction with other platform components.
- Section 4: The conclusion section synthesizes the main findings, encapsulating the key takeaways from the document.

- Section 5: This section lists the sources and references cited throughout the document as background materials that support and complement the information presented in this deliverable.

1.4 Updates Overview

This deliverable builds upon its predecessor E5.2 [2], where the initial prototype was introduced. To clearly delineate the primary updates and enhancements made to the prototype for its final version, the changes covered in this deliverable relative to E5.2 [2] are summarized in Table 1-1.

Table 1-1. Summary of updates for the final prototype

Chapter	Update
2 – Clustering and Classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Offers Data Model: The final all-in-one data model produced for the 6GENABLERS Marketplace offers has been updated. This is described in subsection 2.2.2 <i>Data model</i>. - Functional tests and results: This deliverable adds the report of the functional tests performed to validate the operation of the Clustering and Classification module. This is covered by subsection 2.4 <i>Functional Tests and Results</i>.
3 – Intent-based Discovery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Offers post-processing: The module incorporates robust post-processing mechanisms for filtering and sorting retrieved offers to continuously improve accuracy and relevance. This has been mainly described in subsections 3.1.1 <i>Scope and Functionalities</i>, 3.1.2 <i>Architecture</i> and 3.2.1 <i>Technologies</i>. - LLM model: The model selected was updated from the previous one, i.e. Mistral, to Llama3, which recently became publicly available and present better performance. This is described in subsection 3.2.1.2 <i>Large Language Models for Intent Processing</i>. - Functional tests and results: This deliverable adds the report of the functional tests performed to validate the operation of the Clustering and Classification module. This is covered by subsection 3.4 <i>Functional Tests and Results</i>. - Integration tests and results: This deliverable adds the report of the integration tests performed to validate the interaction of the Intent-based Discovery module with other components of the Marketplace platform. This is covered by subsection 3.5 <i>Integration Tests and Results</i>.

In addition to incorporating the aforementioned updates, each section of this deliverable also provides the overall content initially presented in E5.2 [2] that remains valid in relation to the final prototype specifications. This approach ensures a comprehensive and exhaustive deliverable, covering all aspects related to the automated discovery prototype.

2 Clustering and Classification

At the core of the Smart Discovery system within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace is the Clustering and Classification module, a highly advanced component designed to streamline the organization of a wide variety of offers. This module plays a critical role in improving user experience and enabling smooth interactions, incorporating key functionalities that significantly impact the Telecom Marketplace ecosystem.

The Clustering and Classification module has undergone significant advancements in its capabilities for E5.3. Enhanced algorithms now allow for more precise categorization of offers, ensuring that users can effortlessly find and select the most relevant options tailored to their needs. Additionally, the module's performance has been optimized for faster processing times, providing real-time results and improving overall system efficiency.

Moreover, the Clustering and Classification module now supports a broader range of data inputs, allowing for more comprehensive analysis and classification. This expanded capability ensures that the module can handle the increasing complexity and volume of offers within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

In summary, the updated Clustering and Classification module in E5.3 is a cornerstone of the Smart Discovery system, delivering cutting-edge functionalities that enhance the efficiency, accuracy, and user-friendliness of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

2.1 Final Prototype Design

The final prototype design of the Clustering and Classification module represents a culmination of iterative enhancements aimed at optimizing its performance and functionality. This design leverages advanced machine learning algorithms to effectively cluster similar offers and accurately classify new ones based on predefined categories. The architecture is modular, allowing for scalability and easy integration with the other module of the Smart Discovery system, namely the Intent-based Discovery, as well as other components of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace platform, such as the Offering API. Key features include a robust data preprocessing pipeline, offline training for clusters generation and real-time inference capabilities for managing the classification process. Additionally, the design incorporates retraining mechanisms to continuously refine and improve the clustering and classification accuracy, ensuring that the module adapts to the evolving dynamics of incoming offers in the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

2.1.1 Scope and Functionalities

As a fundamental part of the Smart Discovery system, a set of functionalities shall be provided by the Clustering and Classification module:

- Pattern's discovery across different types of offers available in the Marketplace. Through this method, the offers available at the Marketplace are categorized according to the patterns identified, which facilitates the identification of various subtypes of elements per offer category.

- New offer classification. This functionality allows the system to efficiently determine the most analogous group for a newly registered offer in the Marketplace, in such a manner that it can be properly identified and searched afterwards when a stakeholder places a new order.
- Cluster discovery from the intent subsystem. This function enables the identification of the most related clusters for an offer that has been previously translated through the intent subsystem.

2.1.2 Architecture

The software architecture of the Clustering and Classification module is depicted in Figure 2-1. It is composed of three main operational blocks, which are defined in the following subsection.

Figure 2-1. Software architecture of the Clustering and Classification module

2.1.2.1 Components

As stated in Section 2.1.1, the Clustering and Classification module provides three differentiated functionalities, which are provided by the following functional entities:

- Offline pattern identification function (Clustering): This component is built upon clustering techniques. To achieve this, an offline training process is initially employed to generate several cluster models (one per offer type) on the similarities among the properties of resources within each offer type, resulting in the generation of a set of artificial clusters. To maintain the models' accuracy over time, this process can be periodically repeated, for example, after receiving a specific set of offers or during system maintenance. The training dataset used for those subsequent training procedures includes incoming offers accumulated since the last training session and can be performed in runtime, replacing the current models deployed together in the Marketplace.
- Online new offer classification function (Classification): This component utilizes supervised learning techniques, using as input the clustered offers obtained as a labeled dataset from the previous component. The trained model is capable of

dynamically categorizing each incoming offer at runtime, assigning it to the appropriate cluster. The identified cluster is then integrated into the stored offer information. Additionally, retraining can be initiated whenever there is an update to the clusters associated with the offers.

- Online intent request classification function (Intent-proximity): This component builds on the classification function and uses the same supervised learning model built by that function, to obtain the most similar cluster for the requirements specified by an external user in the intent submitted to the Marketplace. In addition to the previous component, this one also calculates the similarity between the selected cluster and the remaining ones calculated for the same offer type. The objective of this step is to also gather those that have the minimal distance to the selected cluster to provide other alternatives in case of lack of offers availability at that moment in the Marketplace for the most similar cluster.

These functional entities collectively rely on a suite of data structures stored in a database internal to the module, which serves as a repository for data exchange and storage. This repository encompasses essential information concerning, for instance, ML models, datasets, clusters features and standard deviation.

2.1.2.2 Internal Operational Workflows

This section describes the interactions between the submodules of the Clustering and Classification module. The general interactions are depicted in Figure 2-2, where the main blocks introduced previously in the architecture are included.

In particular, it can be observed that four main operations are considered in the workflow, namely 1) Clustering generation from Marketplace offers; 2) Classification models generation; 3) Classification of new offers at the Marketplace; and 4) Intent proximity computation.

The first operation involves the generation of the new clustering models and their storage, together with a newly labeled dataset including the clusters' information, in the database.

The second operation follows a similar procedure with the aim of generating and storing the Random Forest models in the database, that will be used in a later stage for incoming offer classification. In these first two operations only the clustering component is involved.

The third block is dedicated to the classification of new offers arriving at the Marketplace. To this end, the classification component gathers the corresponding Random Forest model from the database according to the offer type and returns the computed cluster id for such an offer.

Finally, the operations dedicated to the intent proximity computation involve both the classification component and the intent-proximity component. When a new request is received from the intent component, the classification service deploys the corresponding Random Forest model, which provides the necessary prediction for the cluster id to the intent-proximity component. Depending on the client's requirement to provide one or more cluster ids for having a wider range of options at the Marketplace search, the intent-proximity component will also search for additional clusters as similar as possible to the predicted one and will return their corresponding cluster ids.

Figure 2-2. Internal workflow of the Clustering and Classification module

2.2 Final Prototype Implementation

The main implementation aspects of the Clustering and Classification module are described in this section.

2.2.1 Technologies

The three functional entities described in Section 2.1.2.1 are developed by leveraging low complexity Machine Learning (ML) models implemented in Python. In particular, the following libraries and specific ML implementations have been selected for each of the three components.

2.3.1.1. Offline pattern identification function

This component is designed to define categories on the marketplace's offers based on their specific characteristics, which are dependent on the type of offer. Initially, clustering methods are utilized to discern patterns within a set of offers sharing similar

characteristics due to their common type. For example, features distinguishing slice offers, like access technology, would differ from those characterizing cloud resources, such as Central Processing Unit (CPU) and Random Access Memory (RAM). This initial process occurs offline using a training dataset that encompasses a diverse range of values for features across various offer types.

The first stage involves generating training datasets with approximately 10 000 entries for each one of the offer types (cloud, edge, spectrum, Radio Access Network (RAN), network service, network slice, and Virtual Network Function (VNF)). The libraries used for both preprocessing and training are based on Python. More specifically, for the preprocessing, frameworks like scikit-learn are used to obtain a clean and properly formatted training dataset.

Once the dataset is ready, two sub-models are designed and developed: Factorial Analysis of Mixed Data (FAMD) and K-means.

The FAMD algorithm aims to reduce the number of dimensions in a dataset with m variables by using k -principal components. This step is crucial for preparing the dataset for clustering, minimizing the number of clusters needed to group all entries. Unlike a combination of one-hot encoded categorical features and Principal Component Analysis (PCA), which is suitable only for numerical variables, FAMD works with all variable types. It identifies orthogonal components that maximize the projected inertia of all variable types, a task not achieved by PCA. To this end, the Light FAMD Python library [3] is leveraged, properly updated to meet the needs of this project.

Once the dimensionality is reduced, a K-means algorithm partitions each training dataset (one for each offer type) into c clusters. These clusters are characterized by the nearest mean and minimal inner variance, aiding in identifying relationships among offers of the same type. The corresponding cluster is then added to each offer, resulting in a labeled dataset. The determination of the number of clusters for each offer type is computed using the Silhouette method, a coefficient that measures the similarity of data points within a cluster compared to neighboring clusters. This step ensures an optimal and meaningful clustering configuration for each offer type. The K-means algorithm is also based on the scikit-learn Python library [4].

2.3.1.2. Online new offer classification function

This model is designed to function as an online tool for classifying offers within the Marketplace. In other words, the ML model is responsible for dynamically assigning a cluster to incoming offers in real-time. However, these offers are initially represented by the original features from the training datasets. To ensure a human-readable classification, the features of the datasets are reversed from principal components to the original features before training, while preserving the cluster labels.

For the classification process, a Random Forest (RF) model is employed as a supervised ML model. RF is an ensemble learning algorithm that ensures high accuracy and precision by utilizing a set of decision trees. In this case, the depth of the decision trees is limited to prevent overfitting. Each tree in the ensemble is trained with a subset of observations, and the leaf node of each tree outputs a specific cluster C (belonging to that offer type).

The final selection of the cluster follows a majority-voting approach. It is important to note that a separate RF model is trained for each offer type, and these ML models are validated using additional datasets containing 1000 entries for each one. The Random Forest model is built using the H2O Python library [5], which permits the implementation of these models supporting both categorical and numerical variables.

2.3.1.3. Online intent request classification function

As stated in Section 2.1.2.1, this component follows the same procedure as the previous one responsible for new offers classification.

When a new intent request is translated by the Intent-based Discovery module as a result of a user search, this component composes the skeleton of the whole offer and requests the new offer classification function to provide the most suitable cluster for that offer type. This cluster identifier (ID) is then used to gather from the Trading DLT the available offers that have been previously registered and classified with the same cluster id.

However, there could be situations where no offers are present at that moment for that cluster id. For those cases, this function also looks for the two closest clusters to the selected one, with the aim of having a wider variety of offer possibilities to be provided to the users, which are given sorted from the greatest to the lowest similarity.

To do so, this function computes the Manhattan distance between the coordinates of the classified cluster ID (in FAMD form) and the coordinates of the rest of the clusters of the same offer type, selecting those with the minimal distance. This distance is computed as per the Manhattan distance as follows: $\sum_i |a_i - b_i|$, where a_i represents the coordinates of the classified cluster ID, and b_i refers to the coordinates of the rest of the clusters computed for that offer type.

2.3.1.4. Local database for internal storage

For information storing, the Clustering and Classification module relies on a MongoDB database. In particular, several associations are created and used in the database. The data management is performed as described in the operations detailed in Table 2-1.

Table 2-1. Database relationship on the Clustering and Classification module

Name	Description	Data type	Operations
cc-sd-sl-data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contains a set of collections, one per each offer category. - Each collection contains a labeled dataset generated for each type of offer. The labeled dataset includes a clean version of the training dataset and an additional column for the computed cluster. 	Tables, Structured data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The clustering service populates this data and updates it when clusters are generated. - When the Random Forest models are generated, this data is used for training and validation purposes.
cc-sd-centroids	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contains a set of collections, one per each offer category. - Each collection contains a table showing, as many rows as the number of clusters identified, and as many columns as the 	Tables, Structured data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The clustering service populates this data and updates it when the clusters are regenerated.

	<p>number of features used to create the clusters.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Each cell in the table represents the centroid of the cluster (average of all the points contained in the cluster) for a given cluster number and feature. 		
cc-sd-centroids-dev	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contains a set of collections, one per each offer category. - Each collection contains a table showing, as many rows as the number of clusters identified, and as many columns as the number of features used to create the clusters. - Each cell in the table represents the average deviation of the cluster for a given cluster number and feature (computed as the average deviation between each point contained with respect to the centroid). 	Tables, Structured data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The clustering service populates this data and updates it when the clusters are regenerated.
cc-sd-models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contains a set of collections, one per considered model. - Each collection contains for each type of offer the generated clustering and classification ML models. 	Bytes, Unstructured data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The clustering service populates this data and updates it when the clusters are generated. - When receiving a new offer or a new intent for cluster retrieval, this data is used to gather the required classification ML model according to the offer type.
cc-sd-offers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contains a set of collections, one per each offer category. - Each collection contains the identifier of the processed offer plus the cluster number on which it has been classified. 	Json files, Structured data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The classification service adds a data entry every time a new offer gets classified.

2.2.2 Data model

The main data model used for this module is dedicated to representing the offer information. To do so, the considered data model is based in the Product Offering data model specified by TM Forum [6]. Using this schema as base, an all-in-one data model is produced for the 6GENABLERS Marketplace offers, which contains all the indispensable child entities such as Category [7], Place [8], Product Offering Price [9], Product Specification [10] and SLA [11].

This all-in-one offer data model follows a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format with common fields across all offer types, as shown in Figure 2-3. In particular, the fields detailed next, which are relevant to the operation of the Smart Discovery system, can be observed. Note that this is not an exhaustive representation of the entire all-in-one model, but rather just the description of the fields that are meaningful for the operation of the Smart Discovery. Thus, additional fields can be present as specified by TM Forum [6].

```

{
  "name": " Sample Offer",
  "description": "Sample Offer",
  "category": [
    {
      "description": "Edge",
      "name": "Edge"
    }
  ],
  "place": [
    {
      "geoLocationUrl": "https://latitude.to/map/es/spain/cities/barcelona",
      "name": "Barcelona"
    }
  ],
  "productOfferingPrice": [
    {
      "name": "Sample POP name",
      "description": "Sample POP description",
      "price": {
        "unit": "EUR",
        "value": 200
      },
      "priceType": "Flat",
      "recurringChargePeriodLength": 1,
      "recurringChargePeriodType": "month"
    }
  ],
  "serviceLevelAgreement": {
    "name": " Sample SLA",
    "description": "Basic SLA",
    "rule": [
      {
        "metric": " availability",
        "operator": ".eq",
        "referenceValue": 99.9,
        "tolerance": 0.05,
        "unit": "%"
      }
    ]
  },
  "productSpecification": {
    "name": " Sample Product Specification name",
    "description": "Sample Product Specification description",
    "resourceSpecification": [
      {
        "name": " Sample Resource Specification name",
        "description": " Sample Resource Specification description",
        "resourceSpecCharacteristic": [
          {
            "name": "sample characteristic",
            "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
              {
                "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
                "value": {
                  "alias": "sample_alias",
                  "value": 10
                }
              }
            ]
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  }
}

```

Figure 2-3. Common structure of the data model for all offer types

- *Name*. String specifying the name of the specific offer.
- *Description*. String that provides a description of the specific offer.
- *Category*. This list of dictionaries contains the specification of the offer type, given by the *name* of the offer type itself and a short *description*. Supported offers type include: Edge, Cloud, Virtual Network Function, Network Service, Network Slice, Radio Access Network and Spectrum.
- *Place*. This field is common to all offer types, except for the software-related resources, namely Network Service and Virtual Network Function. It is represented by a list of dictionaries, containing the *name* of the physical location of the concrete resource.
- *Product Offering Price*. This field is represented by a list of dictionaries, each of them containing the information of a specific price given to the resource. Each dictionary contains *name*, *description* and *version*. Moreover, the *price* field provides through a dictionary the value of the price and the currency. In addition to this, the field “*priceType*” is a string that can take different values according to the followed price model (e.g. flat, tiered, pay-as-you-grow). Regarding the charging, two additional fields are included, namely “*recurringChargePeriodLenght*” and “*recurringChargePeriodType*” to specify how often the payment is performed.
- *Service Level Agreement*: This dictionary contains the *name* and *description* of the considered SLA, as well as the specification of the *rule*, which is a list of dictionaries. Each dictionary contains the description of the performance parameter to be met by the offer, which is represented in terms of *metric*, *operator*, “*referenceValue*”, *tolerance* and *unit*.
- *Product Specification*. This dictionary contains the specific characteristics of each offer type and is particular to each type. Nonetheless, they all contain a *name* and a *description* of the product specification. The dictionary also contains a list named “*resourceSpecification*”, which hosts the fields *name*, *description*, and a list named “*resourceSpecCharacteristic*”, which contains a dictionary for each of the features corresponding to the offer. Notice that is not necessary that all offers display the entire range of features contained in a type, and that at least one feature is mandatory.

The specific characteristics included in the “*resourceSpecCharacteristic*” list are shown below for each type of offer.

In particular, the data model for cloud and edge offers have the same structure, as can be seen in the examples in Figure 2-4 and Figure 2-5. Both offer types share three specific characteristics, namely “*cpu*”, “*memory*” and “*storage*”.

Each of these characteristics is defined by a “*resourceSpecCharacteristicValue*” list of dictionaries. For each dictionary, a “*value*” is provided and optionally a “*unitOfMeasure*”, which indicates the unit in which the characteristic is requested. The main distinction is the range of values that each offer type can take, since edge resources have lower limits than their counterparts in the cloud.

```

{
  "name": "cpu",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": 20
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "memory",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
      "value": {
        "value": 126976
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "storage",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
      "value": {
        "value": 1060
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 2-4. Resource specification characteristics for cloud offers

```

{
  "name": "cpu",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": 2
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "memory",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
      "value": {
        "value": 11776
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "storage",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
      "value": {
        "value": 10
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 2-5. Resource specification characteristics for edge offers

The data model related to the network service offers is depicted in Figure 2-6 and Figure 2-7, which can take up to four different features.

The first one, named “*service type*”, defines the type of network service that is being offered and it follows the same structure as the one described for the cloud and edge offers, but without the need of specifying any unit of measure in this case. Example values for this feature includes `holo_comms`, `UPF`, `CDN`, etc.

The three remaining features named “*vCPU Requirements*”, “*Virtual Memory Requirements*” and “*Storage Requirements*” follow a slightly different structure from the rest. In this case, the “*resourceSpecCharacteristicValue*” list contains two dictionaries with the aim of defining one for the minimum value required and the other for the maximum value.

For instance, for the case of vCPU, the first dictionary contains an alias (“*min-vCPU*”) and another field with the *value* for such an alias. The second dictionary has the same structure for the maximum value. For the case of virtual memory and storage requirements, each dictionary within the list also contains the “*unitOfMeasure*”, which indicates the measure of the value specified (e.g., “GB” for the storage case).

```

{
  "name": "service type",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "UPF"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "vCPU Requirements",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "alias": "min-vCPU",
        "value": 3
      }
    },
    {
      "value": {
        "alias": "max-vCPU",
        "value": 6
      }
    }
  ]
},

```

Figure 2-6. Resource specification characteristics for network service offers (1)

```

{
  "name": "Virtual Memory Requirements",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
      "value": {
        "alias": "min-virtual-memory",
        "value": 24000
      }
    },
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
      "value": {
        "alias": "max-virtual-memory",
        "value": 24000
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "Storage Requirements",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
      "value": {
        "alias": "min-storage",
        "value": 380
      }
    },
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
      "value": {
        "alias": "max-storage",
        "value": 380
      }
    }
  ]
}
}

```

Figure 2-7. Resource specification characteristics for network service offers (2)

Conversely, an example of the data model for the VNF offer type can be seen in Figure 2-8. VNFs can be defined by a total of four distinct characteristics, namely “*function type*”, “*vCPU Requirements*”, “*Virtual Memory Requirements*” and “*Storage Requirements*”.

As it can be observed, the structure followed by the VNFs is the same to the ones of the network services offers (sharing “*vCPU Requirements*”, “*Virtual Memory Requirements*”, and “*Storage Requirements*”) except for the “*service type*” feature. This feature is replaced in VNFs by a new characteristic called “*function type*”, which describes the type of virtual network function being requested by the end user. Example values include CDN, UPF, firewall, xr_player, dpi, NAT, etc.

```

{
  "name": "function type",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "CDN"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "vCPU Requirements",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "alias": "min-vCPU",
        "value": 7
      }
    },
    {
      "value": {
        "alias": "max-vCPU",
        "value": 7
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "Virtual Memory Requirements",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
      "value": {
        "alias": "min-virtual-memory",
        "value": 16064
      }
    },
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
      "value": {
        "alias": "max-virtual-memory",
        "value": 16064
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "Storage Requirements",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
      "value": {
        "alias": "min-storage",
        "value": 320
      }
    },
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
      "value": {
        "alias": "max-storage",
        "value": 640
      }
    }
  ]
}
}

```

Figure 2-8. Resource specification characteristics for VNF offers

In Figure 2-9 and Figure 2-10 the characteristics for the network slice resource can be found. As can be seen, there are a maximum of seven characteristics that this type of offer can accommodate.

The features “*Maximum Downlink throughput per network slice*” and “*Maximum Uplink throughput per network slice*” defines the maximum throughput expected on the network slice for downlink and uplink traffic. As all features, this dictionary contains a name and a list called “*resourceSpecCharacteristicValue*”, which for these two features is given by a list of dictionaries containing “*unitOfMeasure*” (in this case, given any measure acceptable for throughput like kbps) and “*value*” (indicating the specific value of the unit given before).

In addition to this, four more features share the same structure among themselves, i.e. a dictionary containing the characteristic *name*, and a list of “*resourceSpecCharacteristicValue*”. These four characteristics are “*Isolation level*” (describing the slice isolation, and which can be set to “Logical Isolation” or “Physical Isolation”), “*Data network access*” (describing the status of the data network, and which can take the values: “Termination in the private network”, “Direct internet access”, and “Local traffic (no internet access)”), “*Access technology*” (describing the type of radio access, and being set to “4G” or “5G”), and “*Area of service*” (the area from which the resource is served). The “*Radio spectrum*” follows the same structure, but adds a field named “*configurable*”, which is a boolean specifying if modifications are allowed in the radio channel value.

```

{
  "name": "Maximum Downlink throughput per network slice",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "kbps",
      "value": {
        "value": 20000000
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "Maximum Uplink throughput per network slice",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "kbps",
      "value": {
        "value": 100000
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "Isolation level",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "Logical Isolation"
      }
    }
  ]
},
},

```

Figure 2-9. Resource specification characteristics for network slice offers (1)

```

{
  "name": "Data network access",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "Termination in the private network"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "Access technology",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "4G"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "Area of service",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "Barcelona"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "configurable": false,
  "name": "Radio spectrum",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": 39
      }
    }
  ]
}
}

```

Figure 2-10. Resource specification characteristics for network slice offers (2)

On the other hand, RAN offers count with eight features that can be included in the Marketplace, namely “*ranType*”, “*txPower*”, “*bandwidth*”, “*duplexMode*”, “*technology*”, “*operationBand*”, “*centralDLFrequency*” and “*centralULFrequency*”. An example of this offer type is depicted in Figure 2-11 and Figure 2-12.

As can be seen, the features called “*ranType*” (describing either if it is a cell or an access point), “*duplexMode*” (providing information about the modulation and multiplexing mode), “*technology*” (specifying either if the radio type refers to 4G, 5G or Wi-Fi 6), and “*operationBand*” (giving the network band for the radio access) have the same structure. More specifically, the first key of the dictionary sets the name, while the second one (the “*resourceSpecCharacteristicValue*” list) provides a nested dictionary containing just the *value* expected for the feature.

By contrast, in the case of the features named “*txPower*” (specifying the transmission power), “*bandwidth*” (setting the network bandwidth of the radio segment), “*centralDLFrequency*” (providing the downlink frequency band), “*centralULFrequency*” (providing the uplink frequency band) a new key is added to the dictionary included in the “*resourceSpecCharacteristicValue*” list to specify the “*unitOfMeasure*” of the

characteristics. Notice that the first group does not contain this key since those features are dimensionless.

```

{
  "name": "ranType",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "cell"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "txPower",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "W",
      "value": {
        "value": 48
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "bandwidth",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MHz",
      "value": {
        "value": 10
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "duplexMode",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "FDD"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "technology",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "5G"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "operationBand",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": 3
      }
    }
  ]
},
},

```

Figure 2-11. Resource specification characteristics for RAN offers (1)

```

{
  "name": "centralDLFrequency",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MHz",
      "value": {
        "value": 1810
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "centralULFrequency",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MHz",
      "value": {
        "value": 1715
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 2-12. Resource specification characteristics for RAN offers (2)

Finally, the spectrum offers count with seven different features that can be specified, as shown in Figure 2-13 and Figure 2-14. In particular, the features “*duplexMode*”, “*operationBand*” and “*technology*” are identical to the ones described for the RAN offers. In this case, four different characteristics are defined for spectrum, sharing all the same structure stated before in this document (i.e., a dictionary containing value and unit of measure) as follows: “*startFreqDL*” (providing the starting frequency for downlink traffic), “*endFreqDL*” (setting the end frequency for downlink traffic), “*startFreqUL*” (noting the starting frequency for uplink traffic) and “*endFreqUL*” (describing the end frequency for uplink traffic).

```

{
  "name": "duplexMode",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "TDD"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "operationBand",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": 78
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "technology",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "5G"
      }
    }
  ]
},

```

Figure 2-13. Resource specification characteristics for spectrum offers (1)

```

{
  "name": "startFreqDl",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MHz",
      "value": {
        "value": 3650
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "endFreqDl",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MHz",
      "value": {
        "value": 3675
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "startFreqUl",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MHz",
      "value": {
        "value": 3650
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "endFreqUl",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MHz",
      "value": {
        "value": 3675
      }
    }
  ]
}
}

```

Figure 2-14. Resource specification characteristics for spectrum offers (2)

2.2.3 Interfaces

The Clustering and Classification module exposes an Application Programming Interface (API). The involved Representational State Transfer (REST) endpoints are based on OpenAPI specification (OAS).

4.3.3.1 Exposed APIs

The endpoints exposed by this module API can be seen in the OpenAPI shown in Figure 2-15. In particular, three big groups of endpoints, exposed through REST API methods, can be distinguished: cluster generation, offer prediction and intent cluster proximity.

The cluster generation group contains a single method POST “/clusters_generation”, which enables the creation of the ML models necessary for the clusters corresponding to the offline pattern identification function, as well as of the Random Forest ML models to be used for the online offer classification function. Through this method, the synthetic clusters for the offer type specified by the user are generated, in such a manner that a

new cleaned and labelled dataset is created and stored in the local database. The cluster generation also involves the cleaning and preprocessing of the original training file to remove unnecessary features, adjust the input format for the algorithm, etc. This labelled dataset is then used as input for the creation of the Random Forest models.

Figure 2-15. Exposed OpenAPI of the Clustering and Classification module

The first group of endpoints is dedicated to the generation of clusters. Figure 2-16 depicts an example of the input schema for the POST “/clusters_generation” endpoint, which takes essentially three arguments: “mode”, “training_dataset_path”, and “offer_type”.

Figure 2-16. Example schema of the POST /clusters_generation endpoint

The mode parameter can take four possible values, namely “process_dataset” (which only cleans and prepares the dataset to be used by the clustering methods), “ul_kmeans” (which generates unsupervised K-means models in case of having a dataset with only numerical variables), “ul_famd_kmeans” (which first creates a FAMD dimensionality reduction for any variable type and then generates the necessary K-means models), and “sl_random_forest” (which creates the Random Forest models for classification taking as training dataset the already labelled dataset from the K-means model, a reason why this method cannot be used without previously executing the K-means model to generate the such labelled dataset). Both the cleaned datasets and the generated models are stored in the database as described in Section 2.3.1.4. Conversely, this endpoint requires specifying the path where the original dataset to be used as training dataset is placed. Finally, the offer type argument can take as input any specific offer type (e.g., cloud) or it can be left empty. In this last case, the component will generate the models for all the available offer types in the dataset provided.

As shown in Figure 2-15, the Offer Prediction group contains four different methods: POST “/offer_prediction”, GET “/offer_prediction”, GET “/offer_prediction/{offer_id}” and DELETE “/offer_prediction/{offer_id}”.

The POST “/offer_prediction” classifies a new incoming offer into a specific synthetic cluster defined within its offer type and stores this mapping of offer Distributed Identifier (DID) and cluster ID in the local database. The input of this endpoint is a new offer, according to the all-in-one data model described in Section 2.2.2. Notice that only one resource characteristic is mandatory to be provided.

The GET “/offer_prediction” method, which takes no input parameters, provides a list of dictionaries, containing for each of the classified offers the “offer_id” and the corresponding “cluster_id” that was assigned when registering the offer. An example can be observed in Figure 2-17.

```
[
  {
    "offer_id": "string",
    "cluster_id": "1"
  }
]
```

Figure 2-17. Output of the GET /offer_prediction endpoint

A similar functionality is provided by the GET “/offer_prediction/{offer_id}”, which returns the same information of the previously described method, but for a specific offer identifier. For that reason, the output is just a dictionary indicating the cluster identifier by which it was classified.

Finally, the DELETE “/offer_prediction/{offer_id}” method deletes a specific offer from the local record of classified offers given by its offer identifier.

The last group of endpoints has a single method named POST “/intent_cluster_proximity”. This method is solely used by the Intent-based Discovery module when an end-user requests any resource via an intent to the Marketplace. Once the intent-based method translates the user request, this method can be called, to predict the cluster or clusters more similar to the user request, as described in Section 2.1.2.1. An example of the input is displayed in Figure 2-18.

```
Example Value | Schema
{
  "offer": [
    {
      "parameter_name": "cpu",
      "parameter_value": "3"
    }
  ],
  "offer_type": "cloud",
  "various_clusters": false
}
```

Figure 2-18. Example of input for the POST /intent_cluster_proximity endpoint

As can be seen, three mandatory fields must be present, namely the expected parameters regarding the “offer” itself (which is a list of dictionaries, containing for each of them the parameter name and value of the specified features), the “offer_type”, and the wish to find one or more clusters matching the user’s request (“various_clusters”).

4.3.3.2 Consumed APIs

The Clustering and Classification module does not consume any interfaces. This module does not call the interface of any other component within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

2.3 Final Prototype Deployment

The source code for the Clustering and Classification module is available in the project repository (hosted in the i2CAT's Gitlab). Clustering and Classification module repository can be found in:

<https://gitlab.i2cat.net/rdprojects/6genablers/6genablers-dlt/cc-smart-discovery>

The structure of the code repository of this module is depicted in Figure 2-19. In this section, the main deployment aspects to get this application running are provided.

```
├── src
│   ├── api
│   ├── business
│   ├── config
│   ├── core
│   ├── datasets
│   ├── db
│   ├── logs
│   ├── main.py
│   ├── models
│   ├── mojos
│   ├── plots
│   ├── preprocessing
│   ├── routes
│   ├── schemes
│   ├── static
│   ├── templates
│   └── trained_models
├── tests
│   ├── clustering_test.py
│   ├── dropall_mongodb.js
│   ├── plot_results.py
│   ├── timing_measurement.py
│   ├── timing_summary.py
│   ├── tree_generator_test.py
│   ├── utils.py
│   └── validation_results
├── docker-compose.yml
├── Dockerfile
├── k8s-resource-definitions.yaml
├── README.md
└── requirements.txt
```

Figure 2-19. Structure of the Clustering and Classification code repository

2.3.1 Installation Procedures

The component is provided together with a Dockerfile, as depicted in Figure 2-19, that specifies the requirements to be installed and any other dependencies of modules and volumes that must be installed and deployed before the component itself. The default ports required by all the involved applications are specified in this file and match the ones in the project config file (src/config/config.cfg). In the case of changes, the configuration file should be also updated. These dependencies included java version 11, graphviz and graphviz-dev, python 3.8 and pip >= 21.0.1. Moreover, a Docker Compose file is also provided, as depicted in Figure 2-19, for the joint deployment of the python application with the required MongoDB database.

For the specific containerised deployment in Kubernetes, the k8s-resource-definitions.yaml file is also provided, as depicted in Figure 2-19, containing all the required resource definitions. This file includes the specifications of a deployment to manage the application lifecycle, a service of type NodePort to expose the application API in the cluster, and two secrets containing the registry credentials to pull the application image and the application configuration file.

2.3.2 User Documentation

For the configuration and training of the ML models, a set of steps must be performed as follows:

- Edit the config.cfg file in src/config/ directory to adjust all configuration values. The configuration file includes settings related to the server, the data preprocessing of the training dataset (including the default path to such dataset), the FAMD and K-means model, the Random Forest model, and the databases used.
- As stated before, the models must be generated in a certain order since dependencies exist among them. The process to be completed is as follows:
 - First the POST “/clusters_generation” endpoint must be executed taking as input the “ul_famd_kmeans” mode. Notice that this call already involves the data preprocessing. The generated labelled dataset is stored in the *cc-sd-sl-data* database. Likewise, information about the centroids and their standard deviation of the generated clusters are stored in the *cc-sd-centroids* and *cc-sd-centroids-dev* databases, respectively. In the config.cfg file related to the generation of this model, the following parameters outlined in Table 2-2 shall be taken into account.

Table 2-2. Configuration parameter values for the clusters' generation (1)

Conf. Parameter	Values	Description
del_outliers	True	K-means is very sensible to present outliers and must be removed.
feature_scaling	SCALING_NO (0)	The FAMD library performs its own internal scaling process.
categorical_features	ENCODING_NO (0)	The FAMD library can handle categorical and numeric classes.
class_feature	None	K-means, as unsupervised learning method, has no

	feature class.
--	----------------

- Once the cluster generation has finished successfully, the second step involves generating the Random Forest models with the aim of classifying new incoming offers to be registered in the Marketplace and that could be partially completed in terms of features. To this end, the POST “/clusters_generation” endpoint must be executed again taking as input the “sl_random_forest” mode. This model retrieves the information required for training from the *cc-sd-sl-data* database. Once performed, this mode creates the Random Forest models and place them at the *cc-sd-models* database. The algebraical design of this method imposes as mandatory the following configuration outlined in Table 2-3 in the *config.cfg* file.

Table 2-3. Configuration parameter values for the clusters’ generation (2)

Conf. Parameter	Values	Description
del_outliers	True	As good practice outliers can be revised again.
feature_scaling	SCALING_NO (0)	Random Forest does not need prior scaling processes.
categorical_features	ENCODING_NO (0)	The library handles categorical and numeric classes.
class_feature	'cluster'	It takes the clusters selected by clustering methods as main class.

- At this stage, the system is ready to classify any incoming offer that shall be registered in the Marketplace in real-time. To do so, the POST “/offer_prediction” endpoint is used (by the Offering API), setting as input body the information of the offer to be registered. Consequently, the offer is properly classified and registered in the Marketplace.
- Finally, at this point, the module is ready for any call received from the Intent-based Discovery module when a new search request is set by a user. Any translated request from the Intent-based Discovery module can be searched at the Marketplace computing the most suitable clusters depending on the characteristics provided in the offer request. To this end, the POST “/intent_cluster_proximity” can be called, providing as input the schema shown in Figure 2-18.

2.3.3 Integration Guideline

This module is consumed by the Offering API and by the Intent-based Discovery module for the following purposes:

- Integration with the Offering API: When a new offer arrives to the Marketplace, it is received by the Smart Contract State Composer (SCSC), which delegates the offer to the Offering API. In turn, the Offering API interacts with the Clustering and Classification module of the Smart Discovery system to consume its Classification endpoint. This integration results in the determination of a cluster ID for the incoming offer, which is returned to the Offering API for its storage into the Trading DLT.

- Integration with the Intent-based Discovery module: This is an interaction internal to the operational flows of the Smart Discovery system. When a discovery request is submitted to the Marketplace, this is received by the SCSC, which forwards it to the Intent-based Discovery module of the Smart Discovery system. Then, the Intent-based Discovery module translate the received intent by identifying the requested offer type and attributes. With this information, the Intent-based Discovery module triggers the Intent-proximity endpoint of the Clustering and Classification module to retrieve in response the clusters ID that correspond to the user intent.

2.4 Functional Tests and Results

To corroborate the correct operation of the Clustering and Classification module, a set of tests was performed. In particular, the different capabilities of the module were assessed, including the generation of clusters, the training of the classification model, the classification of incoming offers and the identification of associated clusters based on requested offer parameters. The evidence collected during the different tests, in the form of screenshots of the interaction with the module from its OpenAPI, as well as the produced logs and database entries, are presented next.

All the tests were conducted using the component deployed in the project testbed, located at i2CAT. To check the deployment of the Clustering and Classification module the following command can be executed:

```
kubectl --kubeconfig </path/to/kubeconfig> -n smart-discovery get po, rs, deploy, svc, secrets --selector app=cc-smart-discovery
```

This command will retrieve all information about all resources that are available in the *smart-discovery* namespace for the selector *app=cc-smart-discovery*. The parameters to be given to this command are the relative path to the kubeconfig file that provides access to the Kubernetes cluster (if necessary); the namespace name (*smart-discovery*); the resources to be retrieved (in this case pod, replica set, deployment, service and secrets); and the selector to be used (*app=cc-smart-discovery*), since this namespace is shared by the two modules composing the Smart Discovery system (i.e., the Clustering and Classification module and the Intent-based Discovery module). Figure 2-20 corroborates the deployment of the Clustering and Classification module in Kubernetes.

NAME	READY	STATUS	RESTARTS	AGE	
pod/cc-smart-discovery-app-56b4d5df7-98k9n	1/1	Running	0	11d	
NAME	DESIRED	CURRENT	READY	AGE	
replicaset.apps/cc-smart-discovery-app-56b4d5df7	1	1	1	11d	
NAME	READY	UP-TO-DATE	AVAILABLE	AGE	
deployment.apps/cc-smart-discovery-app	1/1	1	1	63d	
NAME	TYPE	CLUSTER-IP	EXTERNAL-IP	PORT(S)	AGE
service/cc-smart-discovery-svc	NodePort	10.107.224.244	<none>	8585:30585/TCP	63d
NAME	TYPE	DATA	AGE		
secret/cc-smart-discovery-config	Opaque	1	63d		
secret/cc-smart-discovery-registry	kubernetes.io/dockerconfigjson	1	63d		

Figure 2-20. Deployment verification of the Clustering and Classification module

2.4.1 Clusters Generation

The evaluation of the Clustering and Classification module starts with the offline generation of the clusters, which as explained in Section 2.3.1.1, is done using the FAMD and K-means models. To achieve this, the endpoint POST “/clusters_generation” is triggered from the module’s OpenAPI as shown in Figure 2-21.

Figure 2-21. Test of the clusters’ generation procedure

This method is executed using as “mode”: “ul_famd_kmeans” (in order to run the two models involved in this stage) and a training dataset initially generated ad-hoc with 10k entries per each one of the supported offer categories, comprising a variety of values for the features of each offer type. Note that the “offer_type” is not used, as such the component will generate the models for all the available offer types in the dataset provided.

As depicted in Figure 2-21, once the module completes the generation of clusters for all the offer types, it returns a HTTP response message with status code 200, indicating the successful accomplishment of the requested task.

To provide a better insight of the performed operation, Figure 2-22 illustrates the logs reported by the module after receiving the request for clusters generation. As it can be observed, the module processes one by one all the offer categories provided in the training dataset (i.e. cloud, edge, network Service, Radio Access Network, Network Slice, Spectrum and Virtual Network Function). For each offer category, the module generates a labelled dataset and the resulting clusters. Note that a bit more than 2 minutes are expended by the module while processing each offer category, which

accounts for a total of around 16 minutes to entirely complete the cluster generation request.

```
Namespace smart-discovery Owner ReplicaSet cc-smart-discovery-app-6d67d7889b Pod cc-smart-discovery-app-6d67d7889b-kfptw Container cc-smart-discovery
2024-05-31 12:46:11 INFO business.clustering Creating FAMD k-means model for resource cloud
MCA PROCESS ELIMINATED 0 COLUMNS SINCE THEIR MISS_RATES >= 99%
MCA PROCESS ELIMINATED 0 COLUMNS SINCE THEIR MISS_RATES >= 99%
2024-05-31 12:48:32 INFO business.clustering Creating FAMD k-means model for resource edge
MCA PROCESS ELIMINATED 0 COLUMNS SINCE THEIR MISS_RATES >= 99%
MCA PROCESS ELIMINATED 0 COLUMNS SINCE THEIR MISS_RATES >= 99%
2024-05-31 12:50:56 INFO business.clustering Creating FAMD k-means model for resource network service
MCA PROCESS ELIMINATED 0 COLUMNS SINCE THEIR MISS_RATES >= 99%
MCA PROCESS ELIMINATED 0 COLUMNS SINCE THEIR MISS_RATES >= 99%
2024-05-31 12:53:12 INFO business.clustering Creating FAMD k-means model for resource radio access network
MCA PROCESS ELIMINATED 0 COLUMNS SINCE THEIR MISS_RATES >= 99%
MCA PROCESS ELIMINATED 0 COLUMNS SINCE THEIR MISS_RATES >= 99%
2024-05-31 12:55:26 INFO business.clustering Creating FAMD k-means model for resource network slice
MCA PROCESS ELIMINATED 0 COLUMNS SINCE THEIR MISS_RATES >= 99%
MCA PROCESS ELIMINATED 0 COLUMNS SINCE THEIR MISS_RATES >= 99%
2024-05-31 12:57:52 INFO business.clustering Creating FAMD k-means model for resource spectrum
MCA PROCESS ELIMINATED 0 COLUMNS SINCE THEIR MISS_RATES >= 99%
MCA PROCESS ELIMINATED 0 COLUMNS SINCE THEIR MISS_RATES >= 99%
2024-05-31 13:00:01 INFO business.clustering Creating FAMD k-means model for resource virtual network function
MCA PROCESS ELIMINATED 0 COLUMNS SINCE THEIR MISS_RATES >= 99%
MCA PROCESS ELIMINATED 0 COLUMNS SINCE THEIR MISS_RATES >= 99%
172.27.13.249 -- [31/May/2024 13:02:16] "POST /api/v0.1/clusters_generation HTTP/1.1" 200 --
```

Figure 2-22. Logs of the clusters' generation procedure

As a result of this operation, as explained in Section 2.3.2, the module stores the labelled dataset produced for each offer category into a database (specifically in the database called *cc-sd-sl-data*). Likewise, the characterization of the generated clusters, in terms of centroids and standard deviation, is stored into the databases *cc-sd-centroids* and *cc-sd-centroids-dev*, respectively.

Figure 2-23, Figure 2-24 and Figure 2-25 show the collections generated for each one of these databases, corresponding to the offer categories. Additionally, at the left, they present a snippet of the stored data. In Figure 2-23, we can corroborate the generation of 10k entries of labelled offers for each one of the supported categories. In the snippet at the left, we can appreciate the example of entries for cloud offers as labelled dataset, where the determined cluster identifier is added to the offer processed information. In Figure 2-24 and Figure 2-25, we can note the different number of clusters determined for each offer category (ranging from 4 in the case of Network Slices to 10 in the case of VNFs). Note that the identifier of the cluster is an integer, starting from zero. Then, at the left, the values for the centroids (Figure 2-24) and standard deviation (Figure 2-25) of some of the generated clusters are depicted.

Figure 2-23. Database entries generated for the labelled dataset

Figure 2-24. Database entries generated for the clusters' centroids

Figure 2-25. Database entries generated for the clusters' standard deviation

2.4.2 Random Forest Models Generation

Next, this same endpoint is used for creating the Random Forest models for classification as shown in Figure 2-26.

Figure 2-26. Test of the RF models creation procedure


```

{
  "id": "SgoErzf25WSgjjzVwUvrGby",
  "name": "Edge offering with flat recurring price",
  "description": "This JSON represents the Product Offering for an Edge resource",
  "category": [
    {
      "name": "Edge",
      "description": "Edge category"
    }
  ],
  "place": [
    {
      "geoLocationUrl": "https://latitude.to/map/es/spain/cities/barcelona",
      "name": "Barcelona"
    }
  ],
  "serviceLevelAgreement": {
    "name": "Edge offering SLA",
    "description": "Basic SLA for Edge scenarios",
    "rule": [
      {
        "id": "latency",
        "metric": "latency",
        "operator": ".eq",
        "referenceValue": 100,
        "tolerance": 5,
        "unit": "ms"
      }
    ]
  },
  "productOfferingPrice": [
    {
      "name": "Edge Product Offering Price",
      "description": "Recurring pricing (flat, fixed amount)",
      "version": "1.0",
      "price": {
        "unit": "EUR",
        "value": 120
      },
      "priceType": "Flat",
      "recurringChargePeriodLength": 1,
      "recurringChargePeriodType": "month"
    }
  ],
  "productSpecification": {
    "name": "Edge offering specification",
    "description": "Edge offering specification",
    "resourceSpecification": [
      {
        "name": "Edge resource",
        "description": "Specification of offered Edge resource",
        "resourceSpecCharacteristic": [
          {
            "name": "cpu",
            "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
              {
                "value": {
                  "value": 3
                }
              }
            ]
          },
          {
            "name": "memory",
            "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
              {
                "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
                "value": {
                  "value": 5632
                }
              }
            ]
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  }
}

```

```

{
  "name": "storage",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
      "value": {
        "value": 140
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 2-28. Edge offer example used to test the offer classification

As depicted in Figure 2-29, once the module classifies the incoming edge offer, it returns the received *offer_id* and the identified *cluster_id* in the response message with status code 200, indicating the successful accomplishment of the requested task.

The screenshot shows a REST client interface for the endpoint `/offer_prediction`. The request method is `POST` with the content type `application/json`. The request body is a JSON object representing an edge offer with various characteristics like name, description, category, place, and service level agreement. The response is a 200 status code with a JSON body containing `offer_id` and `cluster_id`.

```

curl -X POST "http://172.27.13.249:30585/api/v0.1/offer_prediction" -H "accept: application/json" -H "Content-Type: application/json" -d '{"id":"SgoErzf25hSgjsVwDvrGby","name":"Edge offering with flat recurring price","description":"This offer represents the product offering for an Edge resource","category":[{"name":"Edge","description":"Edge category"}],"place":{"geolocation":{"url":"https://latitude.to/map/es/spain/cities/barcelona","name":"Barcelona"},"name":"Barcelona"},"servicelevelAgreement":{"name":"Edge offering SLA","description":"Basic SLA for Edge scenarios"}'

```

```

{
  "offer_id": "SgoErzf25hSgjsVwDvrGby",
  "cluster_id": 3
}

```

Figure 2-29. Test of the offer classification procedure

Likewise, Figure 2-30 illustrates the logs reported by the module after receiving the request for offer classification. This output reiterates the cluster 3 as the resulting group identified according to the offer characteristics.

```

Namespace smart-discovery Owner ReplicaSet cc-smart-discovery-app-6d67d7889b Pod cc-smart-discovery-app-6d67d7889b-kftw Container cc-smart-discovery
172.27.13.249 - - [31/May/2024 14:23:24] "GET /api/v0.1/offer_prediction HTTP/1.1" 200 -
def prediction progress: ██████████ (done) 100%
Parse progress: ██████████ (done) 100%
2024-05-31 14:24:28 INFO business.offer_predictor [{"id": "SgoErzf25WsgjzVwUvrGby", "name": "Edge offering with flat recurring price", "description": "This JSON represents the Product Offering for an Edge resource", "category": [{"
Parse progress: ██████████ (done) 100%
2024-05-31 14:24:28 INFO business.offer_predictor SD_UP_all_location_edge (done) 100%
def prediction progress: ██████████ (done) 100%
2024-05-31 14:24:28 INFO business.offer_predictor Prediction for resource edge in entries cluster price sla-latency sla-tolerance-latency id resource-type place/0/name price-unit recurring-price price-cha
0 3 120.0 100 5 sgoerzf25wsgjzvwvrgby edge barcelona eur 0 1 month (2, 4) (4096, 8192) (100, 2147483647)
2024-05-31 14:24:28 INFO business.offer_predictor [{"schema": {"fields": [{"name": "cluster", "type": "integer"}, {"name": "price", "type": "string"}, {"name": "sla-latency", "type": "string"}, {"name": "sla-tolerance-latency", "ty
2024-05-31 14:24:28 INFO business.offer_predictor [{"cluster": 3, "price": "120.0", "sla-latency": "100", "sla-tolerance-latency": "5", "id": "sgoerzf25wsgjzvwvrgby", "resource-type": "edge", "place/0/name": "barcelona", "price=
2024-05-31 14:24:28 INFO business.offer_predictor Edge
172.27.13.249 - - [31/May/2024 14:24:28] "POST /api/v0.1/offer_prediction HTTP/1.1" 200 -
  
```

Figure 2-30. Logs of the offer classification procedure

Moreover, in Figure 2-31 we can corroborate the addition of a new entry in the *cc-sd-offers* database corresponding to the classified edge offer. As observed, the processed offer is saved adding to its information the predicted cluster (cluster 3 in this test).

The screenshot shows the MongoDB Compass interface for the 'cc-sd-offers.Edge' collection. The left sidebar shows the database structure, including 'DB CC Cluster 1', '9 DBS', and '39 COLLECTIONS'. The main area displays a list of documents with the following fields: `_id`, `offer_id`, `offer_object`, `offer_category`, `predicted_cluster`, and `date`. The last document in the list is highlighted with a red box, indicating it is the new entry being added. This document has a `predicted_cluster` value of 3.

Figure 2-31. New database entry for the classified offer

Finally, Figure 2-32 validates the retrieval of the recently classified edge offer. To achieve this, the endpoint GET “/offer_prediction/{offer_id}” is triggered from the module’s OpenAPI providing the corresponding *offer_id*. As observed, the module returns the indicated record containing the *offer_id* together with the identified *cluster_id* in the response message with status code 200.

The screenshot shows an OpenAPI testing interface for the endpoint `GET /offer_prediction/{offer_id}`. The `offer_id` parameter is set to `SgoErzf25WSgjzVwUvrGby`. The response body is:

```
{
  "offer_id": "SgoErzf25WSgjzVwUvrGby",
  "cluster_id": 3
}
```

Figure 2-32. Test of the retrieval of the classified offer

2.4.4 Cluster Resolution

The evaluation of the Clustering and Classification module finalizes with the testing of the cluster resolution functionality, which is used by the Intent-based Discovery module. Figure 2-33 describes the sample request used in this test, corresponding to an edge offer with specified values of CPU, memory and storage.

```
{
  "offer": [
    {
      "parameter_name": "cpu",
      "parameter_value": "3"
    },
    {
      "parameter_name": "memory",
      "parameter_value": "5632"
    },
    {
      "parameter_name": "storage",
      "parameter_value": "140"
    }
  ],
  "offer_type": "edge",
  "various_clusters": false
}
```

Figure 2-33. Sample cluster resolution request for an edge offer

To validate this capability, the endpoint POST “/intent_cluster_proximity” is triggered from the module’s OpenAPI as shown in Figure 2-34, using the sample input body showcased above. Note that for the sake of simplifying the test interpretation, the sample request used in this test represents an edge offer with the same characteristics as the one classified by the module earlier. As depicted in the figure, the module returns the predicted cluster ID, which in this case, as expected, corresponds to the cluster 3 (which was precisely the one indicated before for the classification of the edge offer with equivalent characteristics). This is returned in a HTTP response message with status code 200, indicating the successful accomplishment of the requested task.

Figure 2-34. Test of the cluster resolution procedure

Likewise, Figure 2-35 illustrates the logs reported by the module after receiving the request for cluster resolution. This output reiterates the cluster 3 as the one grouping offers with a range of CPU, memory and storage that corresponds to the requested offer characteristics.

Figure 2-35. Logs of the cluster resolution procedure

2.5 Integration Tests and Results

Given that the Clustering and Classification module does not consume services from any other component of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, there are not integration tests driven by this module to be reported in this section. The integration tests performed from the Intent-based Discovery module towards the Clustering and Classification module is analysed and reported in Section 3.5.

3 Intent-based Discovery

Within the complex framework of the Smart Discovery system, the Intent-based Discovery module stands out as an innovative component designed to align user intent with the vast array of offerings in the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. This module plays a crucial role in converting user intentions, expressed in natural language, into structured queries, thereby enabling a more intuitive and efficient search and discovery process in the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

Building on its initial implementation, the updated Intent-based Discovery module in E5.3 improves Natural Language Processing (NLP) translation by leveraging prompt engineering in current state of the art of Large Language Models (LLMs), to enhance accuracy and responsiveness. The module's improved contextual understanding allows it to deliver more relevant and precise results, thereby significantly enhancing the user experience. Furthermore, enhanced integration with the Clustering and Classification module ensures that the Intent-based Discovery module can leverage refined data insights, resulting in a more robust and comprehensive discovery process.

In summary, the Intent-based Discovery module in E5.3 exemplifies a significant leap forward in user interaction within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. It offers a seamless and intuitive means of navigating the diverse array of offerings, making the discovery process more user-centric and efficient. These enhancements align with the overarching goals of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project, fostering an innovative and responsive marketplace ecosystem.

3.1 Final Prototype Design

The final prototype design of the Intent-based Discovery module showcases significant advancements aimed at optimizing user interaction and search accuracy within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. This module leverages cutting-edge LLM solutions to understand and interpret user queries, converting them into structured, actionable search commands. The architecture is built to be highly scalable, allowing for real-time query processing and seamless integration with other components of the Smart Discovery system. Additionally, the module incorporates robust post-processing mechanisms for filtering and sorting retrieved offers to continuously improve accuracy and relevance, ensuring a dynamic and responsive discovery process tailored to user needs.

3.1.1 Scope and Functionalities

The Intent-based Discovery module unfolds a set of functionalities finely tuned to interpret and respond to user intent in a manner that optimally aligns with the offerings available in the Marketplace:

- **Intent Translation from Natural Language.** At the core of its capabilities, this module excels in translating received intents from natural language expressions to a predefined syntactic structure, which internally we define as *semi-natural* language. This structure encapsulates essential elements, including the type of offer and the specific characteristics requested by the user.

- Cluster Retrieval for Aligned Intent. Building upon the translated intent, the Intent-based Discovery module further orchestrates the retrieval of the cluster that best aligns with the user's expressed preferences. By identifying the most relevant cluster, the module ensures that the subsequent recommendations and offers are tailored to the user's underlying requirements.
- Offer Retrieval Corresponding to the Indicated Cluster. The final functionality of this module revolves around retrieving the set of offers registered in the Marketplace that corresponds to the indicated cluster. Once the optimal cluster is identified, the system efficiently retrieves the catalog of offers associated with that specific cluster. Before retrieving the catalog of offers back to the user, the Intent-Based Discovery may filter the offers by location, service or function type and/or sort them by price. This ensures that users are presented with a curated selection that precisely matches their expressed intent, streamlining the process of discovering and selecting offerings.

3.1.2 Architecture

The software architecture of the Intent-based Discovery module is depicted in Figure 3-1. It is composed of different internal components, which are defined in the following subsection.

Figure 3-1. Software architecture of the Intent-based Discovery module

3.1.2.1 Components

Figure 3-1 shows all the components and its relation within the Intent-based Discovery module.

- The API is the entry point for the Intent-based Discovery and provides an interface to execute remote operations regarding offer retrieval.

- The database client is used to interact with the intent-discovery database. This database stores a historic of the executed intents and its retrieved offers.
- The intent engine performs all the internal logic and acts as a controller for the different components. The intent processing logic is modelled as a finite state machine, and it is described in detail in Section 3.2.1.1.
- In order to perform some operations such as natural language translation or the offer retrieval given a set of attributes, southbound clients are used. The available southbound clients are:
 - The LLM client is responsible for sending a prompt to the pre-trained LLM server so it can translate the intent into a “*semi-natural*” intent that can be later processed by the intent engine’s finite state machine.
 - The Cluster Classifier client has the single responsibility of sending the attributes from the introduced intent to the Clustering and Classification module and provide back the cluster identifier.
 - Finally, the DLT client is responsible for retrieving offers from the blockchain through the Offering API by using the cluster identified previously gotten by the Cluster Classifier.

3.1.2.2 Internal Operational Workflows

The main workflow is when a user introduces a natural language (or *semi-natural*) intent into the Intent-based Discovery API, and it returns a set of available offers related to that specific intent.

Figure 3-2 shows a high-level workflow of the interactions pictured in Figure 3-1. First, the entry point of the Intent-based Discovery is the API. The intent is first introduced via POST operation in the `/intent` endpoint, passing the `raw_intent` and the language flag (that can be either *semi_natural* or *natural*). The API supports two types of intent: *natural* and *semi-natural* language. We refer to *semi-natural* language a sentence formed with the following structure:

```
<action> <resource> [<preposition or connector> <keyword argument> ...
<preposition or connector> <keyword argument> ...]
```

For example:

```
Discover offers for offer_type=cloud with price=300, memory=2GB, cpu=3,
storage=500GB and location=Madrid
```

The *natural* language approach offers a more flexible way to write intents. For example, the previous intent would look like:

```
I would like to retrieve offers for a cloud service with 2GB of memory, 500GB of
storage, at least 3 cpus, located in Madrid and with a price of maximum 300€
```

However, whereas the *natural* translation approach offers a more flexible way of processing intents, it relies on a non-deterministic Large Language Model (LLM) that may not probably guess completely right the user's intent. On the other hand, the *semi-natural* language offers a deterministic approach for translating the intent, but the user is constrained for the way that sentences are written.

Once the *raw* intent has been received, it is passed to the intent engine, and it instantiates a finite state machine in order to start processing the intent. If the intent is written in natural language (i.e., it has the *natural* argument set by the user) then it is first sent to an LLM server to process the intent and it returns the intent parsed in *semi-natural* language. Then, the finite state machine starts processing the intent in *semi-natural* language, extracting the arguments, and sending the necessary payload for the Clustering and Classification module. Next, the Clustering and Classification module determines the corresponding cluster for the given fields, and then the finite state machine queries the blockchain through the Offering API in order to retrieve the set of offers that are located within the given cluster. Then, the returned offer can be filtered by location and sorted by price, if this has been requested in the intent. Finally, this response is returned in a JSON serialized format to the user through a Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) response.

Figure 3-2. Internal workflow of the Intent-based Discovery module

3.2 Final Prototype Implementation

The main implementation aspects of the Intent-based Discovery module are described in this section.

3.2.1 Technologies

The library used for implementing finite state machines is called pytransitions [12]. It is a python library designed for building finite state machines in a simple, but yet efficient

way. It provides an intuitive interface to define states, transitions and associated actions, making it easy to model and manage the behavior of systems with discrete states and transitions, as happens with the processing of the intent.

The API is implemented in the well-known python backend framework FastAPI [13]. FastAPI is a modern, fast, web framework for building APIs with Python. It is designed to be easy to use, efficient, and to leverage the capabilities of the latest Python features. FastAPI takes advantage of type annotations to automatically generate OpenAPI and JSON Schema documentation, allowing for a seamless development process. It is asynchronous by default, using the power of Python's `asyncio` [14] to handle concurrent operations efficiently. FastAPI also incorporates automatic validation, dependency injection, and serialization, making it a robust and developer-friendly choice for building scalable and performant web APIs.

The project is organized in Python packages that are grouped by functionality. The code is organized as follows:

- The *api* package. This module handles the API functionality. It contains the management of dependencies (i.e., the intent engine), and the endpoints of the API inside the *routers* module. Finally, the *schemas* module includes the *pydantic* classes that are used for data validation in the API.
- The *clients* package. It contains the implementations of the clients that interact with remote components: the Offering API, the Clustering and Classification module and the LLM server.
- The *db* package. It contains the database implementations used by the Intent-based Discovery. For the sake of simplicity, so far, the only database available is an in-memory database implemented as a hash map, i.e., a Python dictionary. However, relying solely on an in-memory database is not always ideal due to its lack of persistence. To address this, the database instantiation employs a factory pattern. This pattern effectively separates the database implementation from the interactions facilitated by the Intent-based Discovery API, ensuring greater flexibility and decoupling in the overall design.
- The *intent_engine* package is the core of the implementation. It acts as a controller for passing objects between the different internal components. Inside of that package there are a few relevant components:
 - The *fsm* package contains the logic of the transitions of the finite state machine, as well as the implementations of the states.
 - The *Intent* class models an intent object and all the arguments related to it.

3.2.1.1 Finite State Machine

As stated in previous sections, the core logic of the Intent-based Discovery module is modelled and implemented as a state machine. Finite states machines work well in modeling systems with discrete states and transitions. Also, they provide a clear and intuitive way to represent the behavior of systems that can be in a finite number of states and transition between them based on input events. Furthermore, the library used to implement finite state machines, *pytransitions* [12], also allows us to execute

callbacks when the state machine enters some state, as well as to trigger transitions according to some conditions.

To that end, Figure 3-3 shows the diagram of the finite state machine that the intent engine uses to process the intents.

The first transition is a conditional transition. If the user had introduced an intent written in natural language, then the *is_semi_natural_lang* flag will be set to *false* and then the next state will be *natural_intent_translation*. Otherwise, the next state will be *semi_natural_intent_translation*. In the *natural_intent_translation* state, the *enter* callback will invoke the LLM client and perform a query to the LLM server in order to get a *semi-natural* language intent back. Later, the state machine will move to the *semi_natural_intent_translation* and will extract the relevant arguments to later on move to the *intent_cluster_retrieval* state. Once there, the *enter* callback will invoke the Cluster Classifier client and will retrieve the relevant cluster for the given arguments. Next, in the *offers_retrieval* state, the callback will invoke the DLT client and will return the relevant offers for the given cluster. Finally, some filtering and sorting of the offers will be done in the *offers_post_processing* state if needed and then the intent will be moved to its final state *intent_enforced*.

Figure 3-3. Finite state machine implemented at the Intent-based Discovery module

3.2.1.2 Large Language Models for Intent Processing

In order to implement the intent processing, i.e., translate a *natural* intent into a *semi-natural* one, we have deployed and inferred an LLM. The motivation behind using an

LLM is the low barrier to infer a general purpose LLM to be an intent interpreter. However, despite the ease of inference of LLMs to be used as an intent interpreter for the use case described in previous sections, running LLMs is computationally expensive both in terms of training, inference and even prompt execution. Natural Language Processing (NLP) mechanisms are commonly used in intent processing tasks like chatbots, virtual assistants, and automated customer support systems. However, they require context understanding provided by large datasets. With very minimal datasets, it is difficult to get accurate results. All in all, we decided to go for LLMs due to the easiness of fine-tuning for intent processing and good performance.

In order to have a stand-alone solution and being concerned about data privacy regarding managing potential sensitive information within the intent processing, we decided to deploy a self-hosted open-source LLM. We updated the model of choice because since April 18, 2024, Llama3 [15] became publicly available. Performing qualitative validations, Llama3 outperforms Mistral for our specific intent classification task.

The model is run under ollama [16], a framework that allows to run and fine-tune LLMs locally as well as expose an API to perform remote operations, such as fine-tune a model or submit a prompt. The model runs on a VM with 8 GB of RAM, 4 vCPUs Intel Xeon Processor (Cascadelake) and 60 GB of disk. However, the most important resource is to let ollama use GPU to process prompts, otherwise CPU usage easily peaks to 100% and the latency to process a prompt becomes extremely high. However, with GPU capabilities enabled, the LLM makes use of the GPU, and the CPU usage is almost negligible. The used GPU is a Nvidia Tesla T4 with 16GB of memory. Although the LLM is answering considerably fast to the initial tests, we cannot tell by now how well it scales if several users are querying the model at the same time.

3.2.2 Data model

In order to submit an intent, the API exposes an HTTP POST method that accepts two parameters: the *raw_intent*, of type *string*, and the *language*, of type *literal* (only takes two values: *natural* and *semi_natural*).

The main data model used for this module is dedicated to representing the intent object. The intent object contains all the state information, which is composed while the intent is being processed. The Intent class has the following arguments:

- *raw_intent*: The raw intent introduced by the user in plain text.
- *is_semi_natural*: A boolean that indicates weather the intent is written in *natural* or *semi-natural* language.
- *action*: Verb of the intent.
- *resource*: Resource or noun of the intent.
- *intent_engine*: Pointer to the *IntentEngine* objects, which acts as a controller. That way, other components can access the attributes of the *Intent* object through the intent engine.
- *args*: A generic list of keyword arguments.

- *id*: Unique identifier that represents the intent.
- *status*: Enum that indicates the status of the intent.
- *offers*: Array of offers related to intent.

3.2.3 Interfaces

As described before, the Intent-based Discovery module exposes an API. The details of the exposed REST endpoints are described next. Likewise, the endpoints consumed by the Intent-based Discovery module are also detailed in this section.

3.2.3.1 Exposed APIs

The endpoints exposed by the Intent-based Discovery API are depicted in Figure 3-4.

Figure 3-4. Exposed OpenAPI of the Intent-based Discovery module

The three provided endpoints are explained below.

- POST /intent/{raw_intent}

As depicted in Figure 3-5, this endpoint returns a set of offers registered in the Marketplace for a given intent.

Figure 3-5. POST /intent/{raw_intent} endpoint input

The expected parameters are:

- *raw_intent*: A string representing an intent written in natural, or *semi-natural* intent.

- *language*: A literal that only accepts two arguments: either *natural* or *semi-natural*. That way the Intent-based Discovery API knows whether the intent needs to go first through the LLM for a translation or not.

After executing this endpoint, the *intent_id* is provided, which is a string containing the identifier of the intent, together with the list of corresponding *offers*, which are available in the Marketplace, as shown in Figure 3-6.

Figure 3-6. POST /intent/{raw_intent} endpoint output

- GET /intent/{intent_id}

This method retrieves an intent object from the module database given an *intent_id*, as depicted in Figure 3-7.

Figure 3-7. GET /intent/{intent_id} endpoint

- GET /intents

Finally, this method retrieves all the intents available in the module database. The expected response schema is shown in Figure 3-8.

Figure 3-8. GET /intents endpoint

- *raw_intent*: Intent submitted by the user.
- *action*: the verb used by the user.
- *resource*: the noun used by the user in the intent. Typically, this is “offer”.
- *id*: a string containing the identifier of the intent.

- status: the status of the intent (IN_PROGRESS, SUCCESS, ERROR).

3.2.3.2 Consumed APIs

As described before, the following three APIs of external components are consumed by the Intent-based Discovery module.

1. The LLM Client connects to ollama as the LLM server. Before, the LLM client was directly querying the Ollama API, but since early 2024, ollama provides an official python client [17] to interact within the Ollama framework. The client provides a *generate()* method that is used to send a prompt to the LLM via Ollama. The method needs two parameters: the *model_name* and the *url* where the LLM is located. The *model_name* parameter refers to the name of the LLM model that is going to process the prompt, in our case is fixed to our custom model “*intent-classifier*”. The prompt parameter refers to the prompt itself in string format.

2. The Cluster Classifier client performs an HTTP request with arguments from the intent in the */intent_cluster_proximity* endpoint of the Clustering and Classification module. This endpoint processes the arguments and returns the cluster ids corresponding to the identifiers of the related offer’s clusters. The expected payload sent to the Clustering and Classification module follows the following scheme. Note that it has a generic structure in order to allow several key value attributes.

```
{
  "offer": [
    {
      "parameter_name": "cpu",
      "parameter_value": "3"
    }
  ],
  "offer_type": "cloud",
  "various_clusters": false
}
```

3. The DLT client connects to the Offering API in a specific IP and port and then makes a HTTP POST request in the */market/offer/cluster* endpoint, passing the list of *clusters_id* obtained previously by the Cluster Classifier client and *offer_type* defined in the received intent, following the schema depicted below. Then, the DLT returns the list of offers that correspond to the initial intent that the user introduced.

```
{
  "clusters_id": [
    0
  ],
  "offer_type": "string"
}
```

3.3 Final Prototype Deployment

The source code for the Intent-based Discovery module is available in the project repository (hosted in i2CAT’s Gitlab). Intent-based Discovery module repository can be found in:

<https://gitlab.i2cat.net/rdprojects/6genablers/6genablers-dlt/intent-based-discovery>

The structure of the code repository of this module is depicted in Figure 3-9. In this section, the main deployment aspects to get this application running are provided.

Figure 3-9. Structure of the Intent-based Discovery code repository

3.3.1 Installation Procedures

First, it is needed to install the dependencies. These are related to the LLM server, the Clustering and Classification module and the Offering API.

- LLM server: Ollama can be easily installed in Linux systems by running:

```
curl https://ollama.ai/install.sh | sh
```

Once it finishes, ollama will be running as a linux daemon. While this is enough to run LLMs, it is strongly recommended to run models using an Nvidia GPU. Otherwise, CPUs will be used, and processing times can be long. When running that command, ollama will install all the needed GPU drivers automatically. Just make sure that Nvidia GPU is detected by Linux. To check so, use the following command:

```
$ sudo lspci | grep NVIDIA
```

```
00:05.0 3D controller: NVIDIA Corporation TU104GL [Tesla T4] (rev a1)
```

In order to perform remote operations in the LLM server, it is needed to expose the ollama API. Ollama by default is exposing its API only in localhost at port 11434. In order to expose the API outside of the machine, the following steps need to be performed:

- Create a *systemd* drop-in directory

```
sudo mkdir -p /etc/systemd/system/ollama.service.d
echo '[Service]' >>/etc/systemd/system/ollama.service.d/environment.conf
```

- Set *Environment=OLLAMA_HOST*

```
echo 'Environment="OLLAMA_HOST=0.0.0.0:11434"'
>>/etc/systemd/system/ollama.service.d/environment.conf
```

- Finally, reload *systemd* and restart Ollama

```
systemctl daemon-reload
systemctl restart ollama
```

- Clustering and Classification module: For the installation of this dependency, check the instructions provided in Section 2.3.1
- Offering API: The installation of this component of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace is detailed in its corresponding deliverable [18].

Once the dependencies are in place, the next step is to install the Intent-based Discovery module. The Intent-based Discovery module can be deployed directly running the Python application or inside containers, either in a Docker environment or a Kubernetes cluster.

- Using the python interpreter: For running the Intent-based Discovery API directly using the python interpreter, first it is recommended to create a virtual environment:

```
$ virtualenv .venv
```

Then, install the needed dependencies using pip.

```
$ pip3 install -r requirements.txt
```

Then, make sure the dotenv file is properly configured with the appropriate configuration.

Finally, the application can be executed running the following command from the root of the project directory.

```
$ python -m ibd.main
```

➤ Using Docker: To run the application as a container using docker a Docker Compose and Dockerfile files are provided, as depicted in Figure 3-9.

To use them just run the following command. This will pull the image from the docker registry from the latest default branch. Also, the image can be manually built from the provided Dockerfile.

```
$ docker compose up
```

➤ Using Kubernetes: For Kubernetes, a helm chart is provided for ease of deployment, located within the helm folder (see Figure 3-9). The helm chart consists of a service, a deployment and a secret containing the registry credentials to pull the application image from the container registry located in the i2CAT's private GitLab. The deployment and service specifications look as follows.

- Helm Kubernetes Deployment

```
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: {{.Values.name}}
  namespace: {{.Values.namespace}}
  labels:
    app: {{.Values.name}}
spec:
  replicas: 1
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: {{.Values.name}}
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: {{.Values.name}}
    spec:
      containers:
        - name: {{.Values.name}}
          image: {{.Values.image}}
          imagePullPolicy: {{.Values.imagePullPolicy}}
          ports:
            - containerPort: {{.Values.port}}
      imagePullSecrets:
        - name: {{.Values.pullSecret}}
      restartPolicy: Always
      nodeName: {{.Values.nodeName}}
```

- Helm Kubernetes Service

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
```

```

name: {{.Values.serviceName}}
namespace: {{.Values.namespace}}
spec:
  selector:
    app: {{.Values.name}}
  type: {{.Values.type}}
  ports:
    - port: {{.Values.port}}
      targetPort: {{.Values.port}}
      nodePort: {{.Values.nodePort}}

```

With this, the helm deploys a Kubernetes service, exposing the service in the IP of the cluster (using the service type NodePort).

The Intent-based Discovery can be deployed in a Kubernetes cluster simply by running helm. From the root of the project, run the following command.

```
$ helm install intent-based-discovery-api helm/intent-based-discovery
```

3.3.2 User Documentation

The easiest way to get started using the Intent-based Discovery module is to run the application and then access the Uniform Resource Locator (URL) where it's deployed using a browser. By default, it will show the OpenAPI user interface. To test for instance the POST /intent endpoint as shown in Figure 3-10, just press the *try it out* button and write the intent.

Figure 3-10. Example of use for the POST /intent endpoint

For a quick test, we can use the following intents:

- *Semi-natural* intent: discover offers for offer_type=cloud with memory=2, cpu=3, storage=500, location=Madrid, price=300
- *Natural* intent: I want a cloud offer with 4 CPU and 8 GB of RAM, located in Madrid, that costs 300 and would like it to be sorted by price.

This request will return a set of offers of type cloud meeting the criteria specified in the intent.

3.3.3 Integration Guideline

This module has integration points with the SCSC, the Clustering and Classification module and the Offering API for the following purposes:

- Integration with the SCSC: When a discovery request is submitted to the Marketplace, this is received by the SCSC, which forwards it to the Intent-based Discovery module of the Smart Discovery system. In particular, the SCSC consumes the POST /intent endpoint exposed by this module API, which deciphers the received intent, retrieves the cluster ID(s) corresponding to the requested offer type and characteristics, and then retrieves the set of offers that belong to the given cluster(s).
- Integration with the Clustering and Classification module: This is an interaction internal to the operational flows of the Smart Discovery system. It is used to map the translated intent to the cluster(s) that best reflect the characteristics of the offer indicated in the intent.
- Integration with the Offering API: To retrieve the set of offers for the identified cluster(s) the Intent-based Discovery module relies on the Offering API. In particular, the DLT client of this module consumes the /market/offer/cluster endpoint of the Offering API, passing to it the list of clusters_id obtained previously from the Clustering and Classification module. This integration results in the retrieval of existing offers classified within the corresponding clusters ID.

3.4 Functional Tests and Results

To corroborate the correct operation of the Intent-based Discovery module, a set of tests was performed. All the tests were conducted using the component deployed in the project testbed, located at i2CAT. To check the deployment of the Intent-based Discovery module the following command can be executed:

```
kubectl --kubeconfig </path/to/kubeconfig> -n smart-discovery get po, rs, deploy, svc, secrets --selector app=intent-based-discovery
```

This command will retrieve all information about all resources that are available in the *smart-discovery* namespace for the selector *app=intent-based-discovery*. The parameters to be given to this command are the relative path to the kubeconfig file that provides access to the Kubernetes cluster (if necessary); the namespace name (*smart-discovery*); the resources to be retrieved (in this case pod, replica set, deployment, service and secrets); and the selector to be used (*app=intent-based-discovery*), since this namespace is shared by the two modules composing the Smart Discovery system (i.e., the Clustering and Classification module and the Intent-based Discovery module). Figure 3-11 corroborates the deployment of the Intent-based Discovery module in Kubernetes.

```

NAME                                READY   STATUS    RESTARTS   AGE
pod/intent-based-discovery-d99786687-8jtkx  1/1     Running   0           4h1m

NAME                                DESIRED   CURRENT   READY   AGE
replicaset.apps/intent-based-discovery-d99786687  1         1         1       4h1m

NAME                                READY   UP-TO-DATE   AVAILABLE   AGE
deployment.apps/intent-based-discovery  1/1     1            1           4h1m

NAME                                TYPE           CLUSTER-IP   EXTERNAL-IP   PORT(S)        AGE
service/intent-based-discovery-svc  NodePort      10.111.76.51 <none>        5566:31111/TCP 4h1m

NAME                                TYPE           DATA   AGE
secret/intent-based-discovery-reqcred  kubernetes.io/dockerconfigjson  1       7m44s

```

Figure 3-11. Deployment verification of the Intent-based Discovery module

3.4.1. Unit Tests

This section outlines the various unit tests conducted to ensure the functionality, reliability, and robustness of the Intent-Based Discovery Module. These tests are categorized based on the components they target, including the FSM handling, intent processing, database interactions, *semi-natural* language translations, and response filtering mechanisms.

The tests are implemented using pytest, a powerful test framework for python. The tests are integrated in Gitlab's CI pipeline, automatically running after a new commit is pushed, in order to maintain software integrity. Additionally, coverage reports are generated during test executions to assess and enhance the areas covered by tests, ensuring thorough validation of the codebase.

- 1) FSM Testing
 - a) Test ID: *test_fsm_flow*
 - b) Purpose: This test verifies that the Intent Discovery FSM can handle basic flow transitions correctly.
- 2) Database Interactions
 - a) Test ID: *test_store_intent; test_delete_intent*
 - b) Purpose: Validates the database's ability to store and retrieve intents, ensuring that intents can be deleted correctly without residual data,
- 3) Semi-Natural Language Translations.
 - a) Test IDs: *test_semi_natural_translation; test_no_arguments_semi_natural_translation; test_empty_intent_semi_natural_translation; test_wrong_semi_natural_translation_without_kwargs; test_wrong_random_intent.*
 - b) Purpose: Checks the ability of the system to correctly parse semi-natural language intents into low-level commands, validating error handling for incomplete or incorrect input formats.
- 4) Offer Filtering Mechanisms
 - a) Test IDs: *test_sort_offers_by_price; test_location_filtering*

- b) Purpose: Tests the correctness and efficiency of offer sorting and location-based filtering within the system.
- c) Sample Data: Multiple offer entries with varying prices and geographical locations
- d) Correct sorting by price and accurate filtering by specified locations.

All the implemented unit tests are passed successfully, as depicted in Figure 3-12.

```

===== test session starts =====
platform linux -- Python 3.10.12, pytest-7.4.3, pluggy-1.3.0
configfile: pytest.ini
plugins: dependency-0.5.1, cov-4.1.0, anyio-3.7.1
collected 10 items

tests/unit/test_filtering.py ..           [ 20%]
tests/unit/test_fsm.py .                  [ 30%]
tests/unit/test_intent_db.py .           [ 40%]
tests/unit/test_intent_engine.py .       [ 50%]
tests/unit/test_semi_natural_translation.py ..... [100%]

===== 10 passed in 0.95s =====
Finished running tests!

tests/unit/test_filtering.py::test_sort_offers_by_price PASSED
tests/unit/test_filtering.py::test_location_filtering PASSED
tests/unit/test_fsm.py::test_fsm_flow PASSED
tests/unit/test_intent_db.py::test_delete_intent PASSED
tests/unit/test_intent_engine.py::test_intent_engine_drawing PASSED
tests/unit/test_semi_natural_translation.py::test_semi_natural_translation PASSED
tests/unit/test_semi_natural_translation.py::test_no_arguments_semi_natural_translation PASSED
tests/unit/test_semi_natural_translation.py::test_empty_intent_semi_natural_translation PASSED
tests/unit/test_semi_natural_translation.py::test_wrong_semi_natural_translation_without_kwargs PASSED
tests/unit/test_semi_natural_translation.py::test_wrong_random_intent PASSED

```

Figure 3-12. Summary of unit tests results

3.5 Integration Tests and Results

This section showcases the operation of the Intent-based Discovery, illustrating the journey of an intent since its introduction to the Intent-based Discovery API towards the integration with the LLM server, the Clustering and Classification module and the Offering API.

3.5.1. Journey of an Intent

The objective of these tests is to evaluate the intent processing ability to handle both valid and invalid intent submissions, ensuring accurate responses and robust error handling across natural and semi-natural language inputs.

3.5.1.1 Successful Natural Language Intent

To validate the processing capabilities of the Intent-based Discovery considering a valid natural intent, the endpoint `POST /intent/{raw_intent}` is triggered from the module's OpenAPI, as shown in Figure 3-13, using the following intent.

Intent: “Retrieve offers of type edge with at least 2 CPUs and 4 GB of RAM”

The screenshot displays a web application interface for testing natural language intent processing. It features a form with two main input fields: 'raw_intent' (required) containing the text 'retrieve offers of type edge with at least 2 CP' and 'language' (required) set to 'natural'. Below the form are 'Execute' and 'Clear' buttons. The 'Responses' section shows the following details:

- Curl:** `curl -X 'POST' \ 'http://0.0.0.0:5566/intent/retrieve%20offers%20of%20type%20edge%20with%20at%20least%202%20CPUs%20and%204%20GB%20of%20RAM?Language=natural' \ -H 'accept: application/json' \ -d ''`
- Request URL:** `http://0.0.0.0:5566/intent/retrieve%20offers%20of%20type%20edge%20with%20at%20least%202%20CPUs%20and%204%20GB%20of%20RAM?Language=natural`
- Server response:** 200
- Response body:** A JSON object containing an 'intent_id' and an 'offers' array. The offer details include:
 - name: "Edge Offering with flat recurring price"
 - description: "This JSON represents the Product Offering for an Edge resource"
 - version: "1.0"
 - validFor: { startDateTime: "2024-10-14T13:50:21.456Z", endDateTime: "2024-11-30T13:50:26.456Z" }
 - category: [{ name: "Edge", description: "Edge category" }]
 - place: []

Figure 3-13. Test of successful natural language intent processing

To provide a better insight of the performed operation, Figure 3-14 illustrates the logs reported by the module after receiving the request for intent processing. As it can be observed, the module first interacts with the LLM server to obtain the *semi-natural* translation of the received intent. Then, the module sends the processed request to the Clustering and Classification module, from where a list of cluster identifiers are obtained (note that in this integration the option of *various_clusters* is set to True by default). Finally, this *cluster_ids* are sent to the Offering API, which replies with the available offers in the DLT for that offer type and classified within those clusters.

```
DEBUG | [app.lbd.intent_engine.intent_engine:42] Processing intent: retrieve offers of type edge with at least 2 CPUs and 4 GB of RAM
DEBUG | [app.lbd.intent_engine.intent_engine:67] Starting FSM with intent: retrieve offers of type edge with at least 2 CPUs and 4 GB of RAM
DEBUG | [app.lbd.clients.ollama.client:18] LLM response: retrieve offer cpu=2, virtual-memory=4, offer-type=edge
INFO | [app.lbd.intent_engine.fsm.st_semi_natural_intent_translation:50] Parsed intent '68005b15-56e5-442b-b019-50b9f9bd1d11'.
retrieves: <offer> <{'cpu': '2', 'virtual-memory': '4', 'offer-type': 'edge'}>
DEBUG | [app.lbd.clients.offer_clustering_classifier.client:27] Payload sent to CC: {'offer': [{'parameter_name': 'cpu', 'parameter_value': '2'}], 'offer_type': 'edge', 'various_clusters': True}
DEBUG | [app.lbd.clients.offer_clustering_classifier.client:30] Response from classifier: {'predictedCluster': [4, 2, 1]}
DEBUG | [app.lbd.intent_engine.fsm.st_cluster_computation:14] Computed clusters: [4, 2, 1]
DEBUG | [app.lbd.clients.dlt.client:20] Payload sent to offering API: {'clusters_id': [4, 2, 1], 'offer_type': 'edge'}
DEBUG | [app.lbd.clients.dlt.client:22] Response from DLT: [{'name': 'Edge Offering with flat recurring price', 'description': 'This JSON represents the Product Offering for an Edge resource', 'version': '1.0', 'validFor': {'startDateTime': '2024-10-14T13:50:21.456Z', 'endDateTime': '2024-11-30T13:50:26.456Z'}, 'category': [{'name': 'Edge', 'description': 'Edge category'}], 'place': [{'geoLocationUrl': 'https://latitude.to/map/es/spain/cities/barcelona', 'name': 'Barcelona'}], 'agreement': [{'description': 'Baseline Legal Prose describing the offering in detail', 'id': 'legalProseTemplate', 'name': 'Legal Prose Template', 'agreementSpecification': {'attachment': [{'id': 'attachmentTemplate', 'name': 'TemplateB2B', 'attachmentType': 'file', 'description': 'Baseline Legal Prose describing the offering in detail', 'mimeType': 'text/html', 'content': 'gMyAwAAWjCCADpls044qWYwqPj4KZw5kb2JqCjQgMGBVYmoKPDwgl18yb2NTZXQgWy...', 'size': {'amount': 1875, 'unit': 'KB'}}], 'name': 'agreementSpec'}], 'serviceLevelAgreement': {'description': 'Basic SLA for Edge scenarios', 'name': 'basicSLA', 'relatedParty': [{'name': 'Infrastructure Provider', 'role': 'Seller'}]}, 'rule': [{'id': 'latency', 'metric': 'latency', 'operator': 'eq', 'referenceValue': 99.9, 'tolerance': 0.05, 'unit': 'ms'}, {'version': '1.0'}], 'productOfferingPrice': [{'description': 'Recurring pricing (flat, fixed amount)', 'name': 'Edge Product Offering Price', 'price': {'unit': 'EUR', 'value': 120}, 'priceType': 'Flat', 'recurringChargePeriodLength': 1, 'recurringChargePeriodType': 'month', 'version': '1.0'}], 'productSpecification': {'name': 'Edge spec', 'description': 'Edge Product Specification offering', 'resourceSpecification': [{'name': 'Edge resource', 'description': 'Specification of offered Edge resource', 'attachment': [], 'resourceSpecCharacteristic': [{'name': 'I2slicer', 'resourceSpecCharacteristicValue': {'value': {'alias': 'slic3_type_id', 'value': '65ca5b5aef00f000a80d946'}, 'value': {'alias': 'user_id', 'value': '65c64afdf050a000910
```

Figure 3-14. Logs of successful natural language intent processing

3.5.1.2 Successful Intent Without Offers

The same operation as before is now tested but using an intent that does not correspond with of the offers available in the Marketplace. To do so, the endpoint

POST /intent/{raw_intent} is triggered from the module's OpenAPI, as shown in Figure 3-15, using the following intent. In this case, the reply provides an empty array for the *offers* parameter, indicating the lack of offers matching the received intent.

Intent: "I need a cloud service with 4 cores and 16 GB of memory in Barcelona for 500€"

Figure 3-15. Test of intent processing without offers

Figure 3-16 illustrates the logs reported by the module after receiving the request for intent processing. The same procedure explained for the previous test is illustrated in these logs, corroborating that for the *offer_type* and *cluster_ids* sent to the Offering API, there are not offers available in the DLT.

Figure 3-16. Logs of intent processing without offers

3.5.1.3 Wrong Natural Language Intent

Finally, an invalid intent is used to test the module reaction to this case. The same endpoint POST /intent/{raw_intent} is triggered from the module's OpenAPI, as shown in Figure 3-17, using the following intent. In this case, the module replies with an error message, indicating that the received intent does not correspond to the considered context.

Intent: “This is a wrong intent query”

Figure 3-17. Test of invalid intent processing

This reply is also reported in Figure 3-18, which illustrates the logs reported by the module after receiving the wrong intent. In this case, the interaction with the LLM server already reveals the incompatibility with the received intent, and therefore no further steps are executed by the module.

```
DEBUG | [app.ibd.intent_engine.intent_engine:42] Processing intent: This is a wrong intent query
DEBUG | [app.ibd.intent_engine.intent_engine:67] Starting FSM with intent: This is a wrong intent query
DEBUG | [app.ibd.clients.ollama.client:18] LLM response: i'm an intent engine designed to translate natural language queries into structured format action resource key\args. In this case, the provided query "this is a wrong intent query" does not contain any specific request or action related to offers, therefore, there is no answer for this query.
```

Figure 3-18. Logs of invalid intent processing

3.5.2. Integration Tests

The Intent-based Discovery module leverages integration tests to ensure proper interaction with the LLM server, the Offering API and the Clustering and Classification module. These tests essentially validate the Intent-based Discovery’s ability to interpret and process natural and semi-natural language queries into offer searches across the modules of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

Essentially, the test environment mimics the production setup with isolated services to ensure accurate responses and to verify the interaction between the intent processing engine, client interfaces, and external services. The tests are implemented using pytest as well, since it becomes really useful specially when parametrising tests for a number of intents. As in unit tests, integration tests are also run in a CI pipeline, in order to ensure that new functionalities do not break previous integrations between modules.

3.5.2.1. Integration with the Clustering and Classification

The test mainly verifies the following features in order to validate the functionality of the Cluster Classifier client:

- **Validation and Processing of Offer Arguments:** Ensures that offer attributes like *offer_type* and *cpu* are correctly interpreted and processed to determine the type of offer being requested.
- **Generation of Valid JSON Payloads:** Confirms the correct transformation of offer data into JSON payloads suitable for subsequent API requests.
- **Cluster Computation Verification:** Checks the client's ability to correctly calculate and assign cluster IDs based on the characteristics of the offers.

Furthermore, in order to test some of the relevant attributes considering different offer types, the test, named *test_positive_semi_natural_intents*, employs a set of offer queries that should return a given cluster and a valid set of offers. The queries and their corresponding expected cluster are outlined in Table 3-1. This test validates that the resulting *cluster_id* for each one of the intent queries is the same as the expected one.

Table 3-1. Sample queries used to test the cluster classifier client

Offer attributes	Expected cluster
{"offer_type": "cloud", "cpu": "3"}	1
{"offer_type": "cloud", "cpu": "4", "memory": "4096", "storage": "100"}	1
{"offer_type": "cloud", "cpu": "2", "memory": "2048", "storage": "50"}	1
{"offer_type": "edge", "cpu": "4", "memory": "4096", "storage": "100"}	1
{"offer_type": "edge", "cpu": "2", "memory": "2048", "storage": "50"}	1
{"offer_type": "virtual network function", "min-vCPU": "3", "max-vCPU": "8"}	1
{"offer_type": "virtual network function", "min-virtual-memory": "512", "max-virtual-memory": "2048"}	1
{"offer_type": "virtual network function", "max-storage": "2048"}	0
{"offer_type": "network service", "min-vCPU": "3", "max-vCPU": "8"}	5
{"offer_type": "network service", "min-storage": "200", "max-storage": "500"}	2
{"offer_type": "network slice", "max-dl-throughput": "15000", "max-ul-throughput": "5000"}	3
{"offer_type": "network slice", "radio-spectrum": "100"}	2

3.5.2.2. Integration with the LLM Server (Ollama)

The goal of these tests is to assess the translation of natural language into *semi-natural* format using the ollama client. The test here simply verifies connectivity with the Ollama instance and submits a natural language prompt that shall be translated into a *semi-natural* one.

In Table 3-2, some examples are shown of how the LLM translates a natural language query into a semi-natural language, so later on the intent engine is able to parse it since it is written in a deterministic manner.

Table 3-2. Sample intents used to test the LLM client

Natural Language Prompt	Expected Semi-Natural Language Response
Can you give me a network service with 2 cores and at least 5000 MB of RAM? It will be used for firewall services	retrieve offer cpu=2, min-virtual-memory=5000, service_type=firewall, offer_type=network service

Looking for a cloud service with 2 vcpus and 4096 MB RAM close to Teruel.	retrieve offer cpu=2, ram=4096, location=teruel, offer_type=cloud
Find a cloud service with a minimum of 1 cpu and 1024 MB of RAM, sorted by price. Price should be around 400€, close to Berlin if possible.	retrieve offer min-cpu=1, min-virtual-memory=1024, price=400, sort=price, location=berlin, offer_type=cloud

This translation can be also corroborated from the GUI of ollama, as shown in Figure 3-19.

intent-classifier:latest
Set as default

You
Can you give me a network service with 2 cores and at least 5000 MB of RAM? It will be used for firewall services.

Intent Classifier
retrieve offer cpu=2, min-virtual-memory=5000, service_type=firewall, offer_type=network service

You
Looking for a cloud service with 2 vcpus and 4096 MB RAM close to Teruel

Intent Classifier
retrieve offer cpu=2, ram=4096, location=teruel, offer_type=cloud

You
Find a cloud service with a minimum of 1 cpu and 1024 MB of RAM, sorted by price. Price should be around 400€, close to Berlin if possible

Intent Classifier
retrieve offer min-cpu=1, min-virtual-memory=1024, price=400, sort=price, location=berlin, offer_type=cloud

Figure 3-19. Sample intents used to test the LLM client in Ollama GUI

3.5.2.3. End-to-End Intent Processing

The goal of these tests is assessing the entire workflow of the Intent-based Discovery module by passing user queries in semi-natural and natural language and validating the system's capacity to interpret these queries correctly and retrieve corresponding offers.

The testing framework is structured around multiple endpoint interactions using the FastAPI test client:

- **POST Requests for Intent Submissions:** Testing the response to POST requests at the `/intent` endpoint with correct and incorrect formats and content.

- **GET Requests for Retrieving Intent Details:** Validating the API's capability to retrieve specific intents and list all intents correctly.

The approach involves a set of parameterised tests where each test case feeds a different *semi-natural* and *natural* language query to the Intent-based Discovery API, which are employed to validate the module response to a broad spectrum of intent queries in both language formats. This test validates that a HTTP response message with status code 200 is returned, indicating the successful accomplishment of the requested task, as well as the existence of the *intent_id* and *offers* in the module's reply.

The used *semi-natural* intents are depicted in Table 3-3.

Table 3-3. Sample queries used to test the processing of *semi-natural* intents

Semi-natural intents
retrieve offer cpu=4, ram=16384, location=barcelona, price=500, offer_type=cloud
retrieve offer min-vcpu=2, min-virtual-memory=2048, function_type=upf, location=amsterdam, offer_type=virtual_network_function
retrieve offer cpu=1, storage=100, service-type=holo-comms, price=50, offer_type=network_service
retrieve offer cpu=8, max-virtual-memory=32768, location=madrid, offer_type=edge
retrieve offer min-cpu=1, min-virtual-memory=1024, price=400, sort=price, location=berlin, offer_type=cloud
retrieve offer cpu=2, min-virtual-memory=5000, service_type=firewall, offer_type=network_service
retrieve offer max-vcpu=8, storage=200, function_type=xr_renderer, offer_type=virtual_network_function
retrieve offer cpu=2, ram=4096, location=teruel, offer_type=cloud
retrieve offer min-cpu=6, min-virtual-memory=16384, price=100, location=beijing, offer_type=edge
retrieve offer cpu=4, storage=200, function_type=upf, offer_type=virtual_network_function
retrieve offer min-vcpu=3, max-virtual-memory=8192, location=paris, offer_type=edge
retrieve offer min-vcpu=1, min-storage=10, price=200, location=tokyo, offer_type=cloud
retrieve offer cpu=8, min-virtual-memory=32768, service_type=dpi, offer_type=network_service
retrieve offer cpu=4, max-storage=50, location=madrid, offer_type=edge

Likewise, the considered *natural* intents are depicted in Table 3-4.

Table 3-4. Sample queries used to test the processing of *natural* intents

Natural intents
I need a cloud service with 4 cores and 16 GB of memory in Barcelona for 500€
Show me a virtual network function with a minimum of 2 cores and 2048 MB of RAM, of type UPF
Get me a network service for holographic communications that requires at least 1 CPU core and 100 GB of storage for around 50€
I'm looking for an edge offer with 8 CPUs and maximum 32 GB of RAM located close to Madrid
Find a cloud service with a minimum of 1 cpu and 1024 MB of RAM, sorted by price. Price should be around 400€, close to Berlin if possible
Can you give me a network service with 2 cores and at least 5000 MB of RAM? It will be used for firewall services
I need an offer for a virtual network function with a maximum of 8 cpus and 200 GB of storage. It will be used for an XR renderer
Looking for a cloud service with 2 vcpus and 4096 MB RAM close to Teruel
Show me an edge service with at least 6 CPUs and 16 GB of RAM. Location should be close to Beijing and price should be around 100€

Find me a virtual network function with 4 CPU cores and 200 GB storage. Function should be a UPF
Get an edge offer with a minimum of 3 vcpus and up to 8 GB of memory close to Paris
I want a cloud service with at least 1 vcpu and 10 GB of storage. Price should not exceed 200€ and location should be close to Tokyo
Looking for a network service that has 8 CPUs and at least 32 GB of RAM. It will be used for DPI services
Show me an edge offer with 4 CPU cores and a maximum of 50 GB of storage. Location should be close to Madrid

In summary, all the implemented integration tests are passed successfully, as depicted in Figure 3-20.

```

$ pytest tests/integration --
===== test session starts =====
platform Linux -- Python 3.10.12, pytest-7.4.3, pluggy-1.3.0 -- /home/sergio/menez/i2cat/6g-enablers/intent-based-discovery/.venv/bin/python
cachedir: .pytest_cache
rootdir: /home/sergio/menez/i2cat/6g-enablers/intent-based-discovery
configfile: pytest.ini
plugins: depinfo-0.5.1, cov-4.1.0, anyio-3.7.1
collected 47 items

tests/integration/test_cluster_classifier_client.py::test_validate_and_process_offer_args PASSED [ 2%]
tests/integration/test_cluster_classifier_client.py::test_get_cluster_for_cloud_offer PASSED [ 4%]
tests/integration/test_cluster_classifier_client.py::test_varied_cluster_calculations[offer_fields0-expected_clusters0] PASSED [ 6%]
tests/integration/test_cluster_classifier_client.py::test_varied_cluster_calculations[offer_fields1-expected_clusters1] PASSED [ 8%]
tests/integration/test_cluster_classifier_client.py::test_varied_cluster_calculations[offer_fields2-expected_clusters2] PASSED [ 10%]
tests/integration/test_cluster_classifier_client.py::test_varied_cluster_calculations[offer_fields3-expected_clusters3] PASSED [ 12%]
tests/integration/test_cluster_classifier_client.py::test_varied_cluster_calculations[offer_fields4-expected_clusters4] PASSED [ 14%]
tests/integration/test_cluster_classifier_client.py::test_varied_cluster_calculations[offer_fields5-expected_clusters5] PASSED [ 17%]
tests/integration/test_cluster_classifier_client.py::test_varied_cluster_calculations[offer_fields6-expected_clusters6] PASSED [ 19%]
tests/integration/test_cluster_classifier_client.py::test_varied_cluster_calculations[offer_fields7-expected_clusters7] PASSED [ 21%]
tests/integration/test_cluster_classifier_client.py::test_varied_cluster_calculations[offer_fields8-expected_clusters8] PASSED [ 23%]
tests/integration/test_cluster_classifier_client.py::test_varied_cluster_calculations[offer_fields9-expected_clusters9] PASSED [ 25%]
tests/integration/test_end_to_end.py::test_end_to_end_natural_language_intents[I need a cloud service with 4 cores and 16 GB of memory in Barcelona for 500€(20ac.)] PASSED [ 27%]
tests/integration/test_end_to_end.py::test_end_to_end_natural_language_intents[Show me a virtual network function with a minimum of 2 cores and 2048 MB of RAM, of type UPF.] PASSED [ 29%]
tests/integration/test_end_to_end.py::test_end_to_end_natural_language_intents[Get me a network service for holographic communications that requires at least 1 CPU core and 100 GB of storage for around 50€(20ac.)] PASSED [ 31%]
tests/integration/test_end_to_end.py::test_end_to_end_natural_language_intents[If I'm looking for an edge offer with 8 CPUs and maximum 32 GB of RAM located close to Madrid] PASSED [ 34%]
tests/integration/test_end_to_end.py::test_end_to_end_natural_language_intents[Show me an edge service with at least 6 CPUs and 16 GB of RAM, location should be close to Berlin if possible.] PASSED [ 36%]
tests/integration/test_end_to_end.py::test_end_to_end_natural_language_intents[Find a cloud service with a minimum of 1 cpu and 1024 MB of RAM, sorted by price. Price should be around 400€(20ac, close to Berlin if possible.)] PASSED [ 38%]
tests/integration/test_end_to_end.py::test_end_to_end_natural_language_intents[Find a virtual network function with a maximum of 8 cpus and 200 GB of storage. It will be used for XR rendering.] PASSED [ 40%]
tests/integration/test_end_to_end.py::test_end_to_end_natural_language_intents[Looking for a cloud service with 2 vcpus and 4096 MB RAM close to Teruel.] PASSED [ 44%]
tests/integration/test_end_to_end.py::test_end_to_end_natural_language_intents[Show me an edge service with at least 6 CPUs and 16 GB of RAM, location should be close to Beijing and price should be around 100€(20ac.)] PASSED [ 42%]
tests/integration/test_end_to_end.py::test_end_to_end_natural_language_intents[Find a virtual network function with 4 CPU cores and 200 GB storage. Function should be a UPF.] PASSED [ 44%]
tests/integration/test_end_to_end.py::test_end_to_end_natural_language_intents[Get an edge offer with a minimum of 3 vcpus and up to 8 GB of memory close to Paris.] PASSED [ 46%]
tests/integration/test_end_to_end.py::test_end_to_end_natural_language_intents[I want a cloud service with at least 1 vcpu and 10 GB of storage. Price should not exceed 200€(20ac and location should be close to Tokyo.)] PASSED [ 48%]
tests/integration/test_end_to_end.py::test_end_to_end_natural_language_intents[Looking for a network service that has 8 CPUs and at least 32 GB of RAM. It will be used for DPI services.] PASSED [ 50%]
tests/integration/test_end_to_end.py::test_end_to_end_natural_language_intents[Show me an edge offer with 4 CPU cores and a maximum of 50 GB of storage. Location should be close to Madrid.] PASSED [ 53%]
tests/integration/test_end_to_end.py::test_end_to_end_natural_language_intents PASSED [ 55%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_get_intent PASSED [ 57%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_get_intents PASSED [ 59%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_positive_post_natural_language_intent PASSED [ 61%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_negative_post_natural_language_intent PASSED [ 63%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_offer_location_filtering PASSED [ 65%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_negative_send_natural_language_intent PASSED [ 68%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_positive_send_natural_intents[retrieve offer cpu=4, ram=16384, location=barcelona, price=500, offer_type=cloud] PASSED [ 70%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_positive_send_natural_intents[retrieve offer min-vcpu=2, min-virtual-memory=2048, function_type=upf, location=madrid, offer_type=virtual_network_function] PASSED [ 72%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_positive_send_natural_intents[retrieve offer cpu=1, storage=100, service_type=holo-comm, price=50, offer_type=network_service] PASSED [ 74%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_positive_send_natural_intents[retrieve offer cpu=8, max-virtual-memory=32768, location=madrid, offer_type=edge] PASSED [ 76%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_positive_send_natural_intents[retrieve offer min-cpu=1, min-virtual-memory=1024, price=400, sort=price, location=berlin, offer_type=cloud] PASSED [ 78%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_positive_send_natural_intents[retrieve offer cpu=2, min-virtual-memory=5000, service_type=firewall, offer_type=network_service] PASSED [ 80%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_positive_send_natural_intents[retrieve offer max-vcpu=8, storage=200, function_type=renderer, offer_type=virtual_network_function] PASSED [ 82%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_positive_send_natural_intents[retrieve offer cpu=2, ram=4096, location=teruel, offer_type=cloud] PASSED [ 85%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_positive_send_natural_intents[retrieve offer min-cpu=5, min-virtual-memory=16384, price=100, location=beijing, offer_type=edge] PASSED [ 87%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_positive_send_natural_intents[retrieve offer min-vcpu=3, max-virtual-memory=8192, location=paris, offer_type=edge] PASSED [ 89%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_positive_send_natural_intents[retrieve offer min-vcpu=1, min-storage=10, price=200, location=tokyo, offer_type=cloud] PASSED [ 91%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_positive_send_natural_intents[retrieve offer cpu=8, min-virtual-memory=32768, service_type=dpi, offer_type=network_service] PASSED [ 95%]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_positive_send_natural_intents[retrieve offer cpu=4, max-storage=50, location=madrid, offer_type=edge] PASSED [ 97%]
tests/integration/test_ollama_client.py::test_get_ollama_response PASSED [ 100%]

===== warnings summary =====
tests/integration/test_end_to_end.py::test_end_to_end_natural_language_intents[I need a cloud service with 4 cores and 16 GB of memory in Barcelona for 500€(20ac.)]
tests/integration/test_intent_endpoint.py::test_get_intent
  /home/sergio/menez/i2cat/6g-enablers/intent-based-discovery/.venv/lib/python3.10/site-packages/httpx/_client.py:680: DeprecationWarning: The 'app' shortcut is now deprecated. Use the explicit style 'transport=WSGITransport(app=...)' instead.
    warnings.warn(message, DeprecationWarning)

-- Docs: https://docs.pytest.org/en/stable/how-to/capture-warnings.html
===== 47 passed, 2 warnings in 32.66s =====

```

Figure 3-20. Summary of integration tests results

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, this deliverable represents a pivotal advancement in the 6GENABLERS-DLT project's mission to transform Telecom Marketplaces. Through detailed design, implementation, and documentation, E5.3 solidifies the groundwork for the Smart Discovery system prototype, addressing the complex challenges presented by the evolving network landscape.

The implementation of the Smart Discovery system prototype underscores our commitment to enhancing Telecom Marketplaces' efficiency by offering a robust mechanism for categorizing and organizing network resources while dynamically adapting to user needs. This prototype consists of two key modules: Clustering and Classification, and Intent-based Discovery.

The Clustering and Classification module remains a cornerstone in creating an intelligent, user-centric Telecom Marketplace. Its functionalities are meticulously crafted to streamline the categorization and identification processes, significantly contributing to the Smart Discovery system's overall success within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

The Intent-based Discovery module, similarly, serves as an advanced interpreter, transforming user intentions into actionable insights within the structured Telecom Marketplace framework. Its capabilities go beyond mere translation, orchestrating a seamless journey from understanding user intent to presenting a tailored selection of offerings.

The architecture, functionalities, and deployment strategies detailed in this document collectively form a comprehensive toolkit for automated discovery. This toolkit empowers stakeholders, from equipment vendors to application developers, to seamlessly engage with and benefit from the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

Reflecting on the progress made in this deliverable, it is clear that achieving resilient Telecom Marketplaces requires a harmonious blend of technological innovation and user-centric design. Challenges related to complexity, privacy, and trust have been addressed through the integration with Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) and the strategic use of automation methods.

Looking ahead, the insights gained from this prototype implementation will guide further refinements and advancements. The lessons learned will inform future iterations, ensuring that the operational components and toolkit for automated discovery continue to evolve with the dynamic telecommunications landscape.

In essence, E5.3 marks not just the end of the automated discovery prototype implementation phase but the beginning of a trajectory towards more adaptive, responsive, and user-friendly Telecom Marketplaces. The dedication to excellence and innovation demonstrated in this deliverable reinforces our commitment to shaping the future of DLT in the telecommunications domain. As we move forward with the 6GENABLERS-DLT project, we look forward to building on this foundation to create a Marketplace that truly meets our stakeholders' diverse and evolving needs.

5 References

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